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Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
1. Executive Summary	3
2. Introduction.....	3
1.1. Satellite sensing.....	4
1.2. Drone based electromagnetic (EM) sensing.....	5
1.3. Proximity sensors	6
1.4. GNSS geolocation	6
3. EOD production technologies.....	8
3.1. Satellite data.....	8
3.1.1. Copernicus Data Acquisition & Processing.....	9
3.1.2. High Resolution InSAR Data Capture and Analysis.....	10
3.1.3. <i>Land classification of buffer zones</i>	11
3.1.4. <i>Ground deformation analysis with InSAR</i>	12
3.1.5. <i>KPIs and technological performance indicators of satellite-based mining site monitoring</i>	13
3.2. Drone based data acquisition.....	14
3.2.1. <i>KPIs and technological performance indicators of drone-based mining site monitoring</i>	19
3.3. Proximal data.....	20
3.3.1. <i>Active hyperspectral sensing</i>	21
3.3.2. <i>Time resolved Raman spectroscopy</i>	21
3.3.3. <i>KPIs and technological performance indicators for the proximity sensors</i>	25
3.4. GNSS positioning	27
3.4.1. <i>Indoor Navigation with micro-simulators</i>	27
3.4.2. <i>Outdoor Navigation with PPP</i>	29
3.4.3. <i>KPIs and technological performance indicators for the GNSS systems</i>	30
4. Golden AI demonstrator – heterogeneous Data Fusion and AI platform	32
5. KPIs of the industry with focus on Goldeneye technologies.....	39
6. Technical performance indicators	40
7. Conclusions.....	42
Appendices	43
Appendix A. Space assets employed in the Goldeneye-project.....	43
Appendix B. Digital elevation models.....	54
Appendix C: European data cube facility.....	56

1. Executive Summary

In WP1 task 1.1 our aim was to collect and consolidate information about current EOD production techniques for the reference including data production approaches, quality measures, throughput times for definition of KPIs by analyzing the current state-of-the-art mapping techniques for the use cases with regards to performance and quality measures.

In chapter 2 Introduction, we introduce the technologies, which will be applied in this project in the exploration, extraction and closure use cases.

In chapter 3 EOD production technologies, we present the EOD production techniques for the reference for definition of KPIs by analyzing the current state-of-the-art mapping techniques and presenting the data production approaches of the consortium. For this chapter, we have collected data from internet research, evaluation of in-house approaches and most importantly the gathering of data from data providers as well as the analysis of Copernicus Land Services and similar reports, in order to identify the KPIs relevant for each EOD production technology.

In chapter 4 Golden AI demonstrator, we present the concept of the Golden AI product (the derivative name from Goldeneye project) system that merges satellite, drone and in-situ data captured into Goldeneye platform. Golden AI product will be the key feature in the realization of the project KPIs.

In chapter 5 KPIs of the industry with focus on Goldeneye technologies, we present a summary of the project KPIs in regards with relevant EOD production technologies.

In chapter 6 Technical performance indicators we present the performance indicators in regards with relevant EOD production technologies.

2. Introduction

The Goldeneye project combines information from different remote sensing and positioning technologies to collect high-resolution data of the mine. The project exploits Earth observation and Earth GNSS positioning data together with data fusion utilizing data from proximity sensors. The data is gathered into Golden AI platform, which combines the information from satellites, drones and in-situ sensors and converts the information into actionable intelligence for safety, environmental monitoring and overall productivity. Data analytic methods and machine-learning algorithms are used to process the data and transfer the information into easily understandable form. The platform created during this project will allow for efficient mineral exploration, mineral extraction and mine site closure.

Figure 1: High-level overview of the Golden AI-platform and sensor data in relation to use cases and applications.

1.1. Satellite sensing

Today earth observation (EO) satellites provide enormous amounts of 2D and 3D time series describing atmospheric and surface conditions over land and sea on a continuous basis, but only less than 5% of collected data is analysed by human analysts. The amount of EOD gathered by programs such as Copernicus will continue to grow with the proliferation of low-cost nano-satellites and commercial EO satellite constellations. However, the use of satellite imagery for mining applications is still in its early stages. The EC 2018 report on Copernicus data use cases lists 3 cases out of 99 possible, which are indirectly related to the mining industry, all focused on subsidence monitoring. In practice, Earth observation data (EOD) and Earth GNSS data remain under-used in the mining industry for the following reasons:

- EGNOS (and its successor Galileo), the EU’s GNSS programme, provides pinpoint positioning capabilities for any asset on the globe that is in line of sight of these satellites. However, positioning data is not available underground or in covered areas without deploying (expensive) pseudo-satellites solutions.
- Copernicus, the EU’s Earth observation and monitoring programme, produces a wealth of data and information of Medium to High resolutions regarding the Earth sub-systems (land, atmosphere, oceans) and cross-cutting processes (climate change, emergency and security). However, it is prohibitively expensive to acquire sufficient resolution (Very High Resolution) EOD from commercial sources supporting actionable insights for mining sites, which are falling back on drone data instead. Also, analysing the data requires a large number of human analysts and Big Data experts that are not typically available at a given mine site.

There are more than 600 EO satellites operating today with satellite imagery offering below 1-m ground resolution enabling mapping scales even down to 1:1.000. The systems can provide high-resolution images with spatial resolution high enough to identify individual ore trucks from the mining sites. Radar based interferometry from satellites has been shown to detect land subsidence in mining applications measured in centimeters per week—a quantitative objective approach that complements traditional ground surveying. Such technology can also be applied in estimation of the volume of material removed from open-pits or in detection of morphological changes in the surfaces of tailings impoundments by means of subtraction of DEM obtained by bi-static inSAR methods complimentary to LIDAR imagery from drones.

The use of satellite data has not been extended to such mining use cases as exploration (mineral detection), extraction (tailing management) and closure (environmental monitoring), because of the difficulty to generate and process high resolution data at a reasonable cost. The increasing trends in cheaper instrumentation and, therefore, lower costs of surveys per square kilometer encouraged a thorough evaluation and validation of these latest-generation methods and new tools by the Golden Eye consortium in support of the objectives of the operational mining applications. In chapter 3.1 Satellite data, we present the state-of-the art for satellite data production as well as the technological approaches of the Goldeneye project in relation to relevant project KPIs.

1.2. Drone based electromagnetic (EM) sensing

In comparison to satellite imagery, airborne sensors (deployed in drones) have a high spectral resolution and they can offer remote operational mapping of secondary surface mineralogy, as surrogates to the mapping of acid drainage-related distributions of polluting heavy metals and indicators of stress in the local vegetation. Pre-dawn thermal scanning from drones can detect and monitor subsurface fires, identify concealed mineshafts and map the extent of near-surface workings. So far mining operators have fallen back on Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (drones), which can support geophysical surveys and provide high-resolution maps of geologic structures for direct targeting of mineral deposits. Drones can embark a variety of sensors (within their payload limits): magnetic, electromagnetic and gamma radiation sensors for mineral exploration, standard cameras for volumes and geological mapping, multispectral cameras for environmental monitoring, tailings monitoring, hyperspectral cameras for environmental monitoring, geological mapping or LIDAR for volumes of rock piles or tailing ponds, geological mapping, geomorphological studies. However, drones have limitations, such as electromagnetic interference between drone and sensors, limited payload capacity, short flight times, difficulty to penetrate vegetation cover, which makes them a complement (rather than a competitor) to other Earth observation data methods. In fact, drone data can be used to help calibrate the satellite sensors or annotate the resulting high-resolution maps. In chapter 3.2 Drone based data acquisition, we present the state-of-the art for aerial surveys as well as the technological approaches of the Goldeneye project in relation to relevant project KPIs.

1.3. Proximity sensors

The aerial imaging technologies are a powerful tool for analysing large surface areas to detect anomalies, environmental changes and geophysical differences in the mining sites. However, they are not able to give precise information on the mine site mineralogy without additional proximity sensors used to complement and calibrate the mineralogical maps. In the mining sector, different spectroscopic sensors have been deployed to improve mineral identification in laboratory settings, but onsite detection is still under progress. Spectroscopy, in general, can do fast molecular identification and quantification of different minerals. The information gathered can be used in exploration to find the valuable mineral deposits as well as in mining to focus the extraction to the right type of ore and improve the ore processing getting better mineral and metal products with lower energy and chemical use. Goldeneye-project will develop the use of ground-based sensors deployed on mining equipment and used on the mining sites including time-gated Raman spectrometers for non-destructive precise mineralogical analysis in the field and active hyperspectral spectrometers for remote screening of larger areas with high measurement distances under any ambient light conditions (with and without sunlight). Commercial XRF spectrometers will be used for calibration and verification of drone and proximal sensing data. Ground sensors will also be extremely useful for the identification of secondary minerals (e.g. W, In, Sb, Au in Germany; Au, Cu in Bulgaria; and Ge, Ga, In, Se, Te in Kosovo), which might not be detected by other observation methods. In chapter 3.3 Proximal data, we present the state-of-the art for Raman and hyperspectral sensing as well as the technological approaches of the Goldeneye project in relation to relevant project KPIs.

1.4. GNSS geolocation

Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) refers to a group of satellites providing data from space on positioning and timing to GNSS receivers located on Earth. These satellites carry very stable atomic clocks that are synchronized with the ground clocks. The receivers then use this data to determine their location. There has been a study showing that a 30-day loss of GNSS location services could amount to 1 billion dollar per day for the global economy (O'Connor, Alan C., et al. Economic benefits of the global positioning system (gps). No. RTI Project Number 0215471. RTI International, 2019). As close as 20 years ago, it was hard to imagine that satellite positioning could have such an impact on our daily lives. GNSS provides global coverage through several satellites including Europe's Galileo, the USA's NAVSTAR Global Positioning System (GPS), Russia's Global'naya Navigatsionnaya Sputnikovaya Sistema (GLONASS) and China's BeiDou Navigation Satellite System. Various suppliers (e.g. Qualcomm, Broadcom, u-blox, Mediatek, STMicro, Sony) offer GNSS geolocation solutions and constantly seek ways to decrease cost, improve accuracy and reduce power consumption using advances in signal processing. However, there are some challenging situations in geolocation. As an example, buildings may sometimes obstruct or reflect the signals from the satellites, and this is particularly difficult challenge due to signal reflections causing multi-path errors. GNSS vendors have been trying to solve the issues with advanced signal processing approaches such as narrow correlators or double delta discriminators. However, these

approaches are generating longer TTFFs (time to first fix) and higher power consumption. In addition, these systems have severe limitation in enclosed environments such as underground mines. On the other hand, cellular networks (3G, 4G, 5G, LoRa) can provide positioning services based on cell ID, Time Difference of Arrival (TDOA) or Advanced Forward Link Triangulation (AFLT) even in enclosed spaces. However, the cell ID method provides low accuracy and the other methods tend to generate high power consumption of the device. Other positioning solutions adapted to indoor settings are based on network fingerprinting (Wi-Fi) or wireless beacons (Bluetooth, Li-Fi, RFID). These solutions require a dense network of nodes, which generates substantial infrastructure costs incompatible with mine operator financial requirements. The Goldeneye GNSS in-mine geolocation system with GNSS micro-simulators will address these challenges in the setting of underground mine with the targets of increased employee safety and prevention of personnel entering banned areas as well as location assistance in case of emergencies to help to locate the person(s) in distress. In chapter 3.4 GNSS positioning, we present the state-of-the art for indoor and outdoor positioning as well as the technological approaches of the Goldeneye project in relation to relevant project KPIs.

3. EOD production technologies

3.1. Satellite data

Although the satellite imagery can achieve high ground resolution in 1-m scale, cloud cover can obstruct the vision and prevent the analysis of a mining site. Due to frequent obstructions of the view by the clouds, monitoring of the Earth surface using SAR satellite radar has been gaining interest as it can perform with almost any cloud condition. Also SAR is increasingly used to perform change detection, conduct remote measurements of the physical properties of the surface, which are useful for prevention of natural and anthropological hazards. For example, Differential

Interferometry SAR (DInSAR) and Persistent Scatterer Interferometry SAR (PSInSAR) are used for detecting ground deformation and SAR polarimetry is used for moisture and water presence detection, vegetation monitoring and human activity mapping. Radar interferometry from satellites has been shown to detect subsidence in mining in terms of centimeters per month — a quantitative objective approach that complements traditional ground surveying. Such technology can also be applied in estimation of the volume of material removed from open-pits or in detection of morphological changes in the surfaces of tailings impoundments.

Figure 2. Ground resolution <1-m scale in VHR SAR image from TSX of a large city (by Airbus DS).

New generation of SAR space borne or airborne instruments provide the remote sensing products with sub-meter resolution, allowing for computing very accurate interferograms and polarimetry capable for slow and dynamic subsidence detection over even small areas, slope stability measurements, human activity and biomass monitoring which are very important in populated mining regions, where mining activities can damage residential buildings and mining ground infrastructures.

The Goldeneye project will enable novel uses of Earth observation and Earth GNSS data in the mining industry:

- The project will use Copernicus and other contributing mission data for precise surface change detection regardless of cloud cover and time of the day. **Appendix A**

- We will use interferometric SAR (InSAR) Level 1 SLC data combined with Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and Surface Elevation Models (SEM) obtained from LIDAR instruments.

Appendix B

- Using super-resolution and data fusion technologies, we will get the global scale and temporal resolution of the Copernicus program as well as the necessary details required for monitoring of mines. **Chapter 2.5**
- The project will use several Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) and regional Copernicus partner hubs as well as other cloud providers hosting satellite data, benefiting from the Sentinel Hub's federation. **Appendix C**

3.1.1. Copernicus Data Acquisition & Processing

European Copernicus Earth Observation was mandated by the European Parliament in 2014.¹ Copernicus Earth Observation programme provides reliable and reasonably up-to-date services (typically within 5-6h delay from acquisition time by the satellite) on the sustainable basis. These multi-platform heterogeneous EOD (Earth Observation Data) sources serve the needs of the European industry and will be used extensively during the work on Goldeneye project activities. The existing Copernicus service components to be used in the project are the Space component and the Service component. The remaining In-situ component will not be used in the project, as the in-situ data will be provided from the respective partners in the scope of the WP3 and WP4 of the project.

The Copernicus Space component will be the primary source of EOD as it provides the consortium with the cost-efficient space-based remote sensing data of the broad nature on a frequent basis. The Copernicus Space segment consists of a constellation of the dedicated missions with the specific goals and is represented by the fleet of Sentinel satellite platforms as well as other contributing missions, which include commercial platforms and platforms jointly developed through the international collaboration. The data from these additional sources will be used in the project in order to augment the Copernicus Space component EOD with very high-resolution products from commercial missions and to provide additional missing spectral bands and needed geophysical measurements (i.e. gravitational maps).

The Copernicus Service component provides the products generated from the Copernicus Space and Copernicus In-situ components. These services consist of six thematic areas out of which the Goldeneye project will use the Land Monitoring Service products and potentially Emergency Management Service if the need arises during the project activities. The Copernicus Land Monitoring service will provide historical and reference data to be used in the cases covering environmental protection, monitoring of the areas with urban (human) activity in support of sustainable and responsible development practices directly related to the exploration, exploitation, closure and post-closure activities at the project's Field Sites. There is (potentially) an interest and this far unexplored possibility to interface to the Copernicus Security service data for the support of the

¹ REGULATION (EU) No 377/2014 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 3 April 2014 establishing the Copernicus Programme and repealing Regulation (EU) No 911/2010

monitoring and reporting of the potential technological and man-made emergencies (e.g. industrial accidents) and support of the intervention cycle activities from early warning to active crisis management and recovery.

3.1.2. High Resolution InSAR Data Capture and Analysis

We will use DInSAR and PSInSAR to map surface deformations (e.g. landslides, surface subsidence) and detect surface changes rapidly and precisely.

We will use Sentinel 1 C-band dual-polarization Interferometric Wide Swath Mode SLC Level 1 (see right illustration) and Terra-SAR X-band dual-polarization Strip-Mode SLC Level 1. With Sentinel 1A and 1B data used concurrently, it is feasible to acquire InSAR suitable imagery for the specific area every 3-7 (6) days for the pilot sites located in mid-latitudes in northern and southern hemispheres. For the equatorial and sparsely populated areas outside of the Eurasian continent we expect monthly imagery (every 24 (12) days) that is suitable for InSAR analysis.

Copernicus Earth observation data will be processed directly from DIAS data stores or accessed via the SCI portal. Additional very high-resolution data (at least 3m/pixel) will be acquired from Airbus DS directly or via the SCI portal.

The project will use artificial intelligence (AI) technology from partner OPT derived from space-worthy ESA technology obtained under the ESA technology transfer program. The AI platform works with structured and unstructured data and is particularly suitable for use in unstructured environments. Unlike other approaches, it does not require high quality labelled AI training datasets and can begin detecting known and unknown anomalies very rapidly, which makes it particularly applicable for the selected use cases, allowing to learn and automate complex time-intensive EOD analysis tasks. The solution will be able of processing at least 1,5TB of Sentinel 1 InSAR data per day and processing a scene of 100,000km² (at 13mx5m resolution) in 5 min. For high precision commercial InSAR data DAR will process the data in-house in a several days after last acquisition date and provide the processed deformation maps to the consortium partners.

Figure 3. The InSAR methodology involves acquiring two SAR images of the same area at different times. If the surface moves between the two acquisitions a phase shift occurs and an interferogram is able to map surface deformations.

3.1.3. Land classification of buffer zones

For mining enterprises, monitoring of the environmental impact of the adjacent territories consists in periodically assessing the state of vegetation within the buffer zones of mining facilities (mines, quarries, dumps, tailings, etc.). Assessment of the state of vegetation is carried out by constructing cartograms of vegetation indices and tracking their changes over time. Mining areas are usually characterized by high values of land surface temperature (LST). Remote sensing data in the thermal region of the electromagnetic spectrum allow to assess the LST and to detect surface and subsurface processes characterized by intensive heat release. According to literature temperature mapping technologies of mining territories are used to solve the following problems:

- environmental assessment - a decrease in LST at mining areas may be associated with an improvement in environmental quality;
- monitoring of heat island phenomenon.

In Goldeneye-project, EOS will perform continuous monitoring of mining processes and ecological conditions of mining areas with the construction of buffer zones. The assessment of mining operations impact on the environment includes the evaluation of the number of buildings and planted areas within the buffer zones. EOS will automate the calculation of temperature indicators of waste dumps surface and adjacent buffer zones by using optical data with thermal bands.

EOS will acquire gravimetric data from GRACE satellites (level 2 and level 3) and provide via OGC compliant data search and retrieval APIs. This will enable to support the analysis and visualization

of gravimetric maps alongside other data layers such as multispectral maps and interferograms based on Sentinel-1 satellite pairs for data fusion purposes.

Additionally EOS can deliver open access land classification datasets:

- Corine Land Cover 2018, CLC2018 (spatial resolution - 100 m, data layers available for 1990, 2000, 2006, 2012, 2018);
- MODIS Land Cover Type/Dynamics MCD12Q1 (spatial resolution - 100 m, annual product);
- ESA Climate Change Initiative (CCI) Land Cover Map 2015 (spatial resolution - 300 m, data layers available for 1992-2015);
- Sentinel-2 Global Land Cover, S2GLC 2017 (spatial resolution - 10 m, data layers available for 2017).
- The use and validation of EOS technology in the mining sector has been previously studied in mining regions of Ukraine (Donetsk Coal Basin, Nikopol Manganese Basin, etc.). The results of commercial projects include:
- Ecological condition indicators of slagheap landscapes in coal-industrial regions of Ukraine
- Temperature indicators of industrial enterprises effect on the environment and adjacent territories
- Vertical displacement maps for industrial areas of the central part of Ukraine, surface subsidence velocity estimation in the mining areas of Ukraine.

3.1.4. Ground deformation analysis with InSAR

In mining sector, InSAR technology is currently used to monitor surface ground deformations and control settlements and slope stability in different facilities, such as open pits, tailings dams, waste dumps, leach pads and infrastructures. Different satellite constellations are most commonly used, such as SENTINEL-1, COSMO SkyMed, TERRASAR-X, TANDEM-X and PAZ, all from European providers. All these satellites incorporate RADAR sensors to obtain both topographic data and deformation data over time. The revisiting time for these satellite constellations is a few days. New measurements of ground deformation can be refreshed within days.

In Goldeneye project, DARES will provide InSAR analytics to enable novel uses of Earth observation data in the mining industry:

- The project will use interferometric SAR (InSAR) Level 1 SLC data combined with Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and Surface Elevation Models (SEM) obtained from LIDAR instruments. Using super-resolution and data fusion technologies, we will get the global scale and temporal resolution of the Copernicus program as well as the necessary details required for monitoring of mines. The project will use several Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) and

regional Copernicus partner hubs as well as other cloud providers hosting satellite data, benefiting from the Sentinel Hub's federation.

3.1.5. KPIs and technological performance indicators of satellite-based mining site monitoring

InSAR Technology performance level depends on the coherence of the interferograms (from the satellite RADAR images), which generally depends on the land cover, moisture conditions and atmospheric conditions over the area of interest. The indicators for performance are the density of measured points and minimum coherence (quality) required. With more than 9.5M scenes (more than 10.000 added every day) available covering over 90Bn km² of area and containing almost a quadrillion of pixels, Sentinel-2 is becoming one of the most important EO datasets in the world. Acquiring and processing the large amounts of available data is a major challenge arising in Earth Observation, that requires remote sensing, big data and cloud expertise.

The near real-time processing Sentinel Hub service from Sinergise allows to break away from the traditional processing chains and supply OPT-NET's platform with on-demand analysis ready data on-the-fly. The solution will make available a full (multi-temporal and multi-spectral) Sentinel-2 archive, accessible via a web service, allowing to query Sentinel data anywhere in the world and fuse it among various missions as well as with other data streams of the Goldeneye project. The Sentinel-2 data provided via Sentinel Hub services are in line with the project's key performance indicators defined for EO data in terms of spatial and temporal resolution, as well as processing throughput, that could not be reached with competing data-sources.

The Golden AI platform will fuse, analyse all time-series EO data from the partners involved, offering an unprecedented level of optimization for planning the test drilling areas (KPI 1, 10) as well as tools for better control of environmental impact of mines (KPI 2, 11). In addition, The data fusion offers the mines tools to reduce their operational costs (KPI 6,9) as well as to optimize the used resources (KPI 12).

The AI platform will fuse, analyse all time-series EO data from the partners involved utilizing Copernicus derived services provided by Dares, EOS and Sinergise (KPI 12).

Table 1. Indication of relevant Key performance indicators for SWIR imaging, Gravitational, Elevation and SAR data.

<i>KPI description</i>	<i>KPI no</i>	<i>SWIR imaging</i>	<i>Gravitational data</i>	<i>Elevation data</i>	<i>SAR data for anomalies</i>
Reduced drilling costs by 40%	1		✓	✓	✓
Reduced environmental impact due to less immersive techniques	2	✓		✓	✓
New Sn, W, Sb, In, Cu and Au mineral deposits in Germany and Bulgaria	3	✓	✓	✓	✓
Ge, Ga, In, Se, Te content in the run-of mine ore	4				
120 jobs over the next 5 years for consortium partners	5				
Net Present Value of Goldeneye investment between €2M and €29M per site over 5 years (depending on size)	6	✓			✓
50% < Internal Rate of Return < 100% for all site operators over 5 years	7				
Production of 0.5m Digital Elevation Maps on weekly basis with <0.5m vertical accuracy (RMSE)	8				
At least 10 scientific publications, at least 2 educational courses (PDAC, IGC), at least 5 new patents filings	9	✓			✓
Reduced environmental impact due to less drilling required	10	✓			✓
Zero accident on mining sites protecting the community and the environment. Zero environmental pollution	11	✓		✓	✓
At least 5 new Copernicus-derived services focusing on mineral detection, safety, geo-hazards, environmental monitoring and operations management	12	✓	✓	✓	✓

3.2. Drone based data acquisition

During the past decade, UAV's and drones have emerged as survey tools for different applications in various stages of exploration, extraction and reclamation in the mining industry. The advantage of drones is that they enable accessing challenging areas with difficult or dangerous topographies. In addition, they provide information with improved resolution which can be used for calibrating and planning satellite surveys or aerial missions. In general, current UAV-applications can be categorized into 9 categories²:

1. Geological and structural analysis via remote sensing (RGB, HIS)
2. Aerial geophysical survey at the exploration phase (Magnetic)
3. Topographic surveying in open-pit mines (RGB)

² Park, Sebeom, and Yosoon Choi. "Applications of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles in Mining from Exploration to Reclamation: A Review." *Minerals* 10.8 (2020): 663.

4. Rock slope analysis (RGB)
5. Working environment analysis (RGB)
6. Surveying in underground mines at the exploitation phase (RGB, Thermal, Multispectral)
7. Soil and water pollution monitoring (Gamma spectrum, Hyperspectral, Temperature data)
8. Ecological restoration monitoring (RGB, Multispectral)
9. Ground subsidence monitoring at the reclamation phase (RGB)

The most widely recorded data in UAV surveys are RGB images. Such data can be utilized e.g. in creation of high-resolution 3D-models of hard-to-access outcrops³. RGB-data can also be used to create ortho-mosaic maps and digital surface models of open-pit mines^{4,5}. The recent development of smaller sensors has also enabled for the drones to carry hyperspectral and multispectral cameras that give spectral information on each pixel of the image. Such data has been used in mapping of lithology⁶ and accumulated iron in soil⁷. In addition, drones have been utilised in collecting geophysical magnetic field data⁸, which can complement optical remote sensing data when identifying geological features and ore extents⁹. Other uses for UAVs in the mining industry include capturing water temperature data to determine the optimal sampling depth of a pit lake,¹⁰ and measuring gamma spectrum data to map uranium veins and mapping of dust plumes created by blasting¹¹.

Most of the existing aerial surveys performed on site are traditional in nature and do not cover an entire site. Additionally, given that significant resources and costs would be involved, such surveys

³ Madjid, M.Y.A.; Vandeginste, V.; Hampson, G.; Jordan, C.J.; Booth, A.D. Drones in carbonate geology: Opportunities and challenges, and application in diagenetic dolomite geobody mapping. *Mar. Pet. Geol.* **2018**, *91*, 723–734.

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⁵ Lee, S.; Choi, Y. On-site demonstration of topographic surveying techniques at open-pit mines using a fixed-wing unmanned aerial vehicle (drone). *Tunn. Undergr. Space* **2015**, *25*, 462–468.

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⁹ Jackisch, R.; Madriz, Y.; Zimmermann, R.; Pirttijärvi, M.; Saartenoja, A.; Heincke, B.H.; Salmirinne, H.; Kujasalo, J.-P.; Andreani, L.; Gloaguen, R.; et al. Drone-Borne Hyperspectral and Magnetic Data Integration: Otanmäki Fe-Ti-V Deposit in Finland. *Remote Sens.* **2019**, *11*, 2084.

¹⁰ Martin, P.G.; Payton, O.D.; Fardoulis, J.S.; Richards, D.A.; Scott, T.B. The use of unmanned aerial systems for the mapping of legacy uranium mines. *J. Environ. Radioact.* **2015**, *143*, 135–140.

¹¹ Alvarado, M.; Gonzalez, F.; Fletcher, A.; Doshi, A. Towards the development of a low cost airborne sensing system to monitor dust particles after blasting at open-pit mine sites. *Sensors* **2015**, *15*, 19667–19687.

often rely on statistical sampling and they do not cover the entire site, rather only focus on specific areas of the mining site. Additionally, the data points used for such surveys is often heavily aggregated, making the data sets sparse and not accurate enough. As an example, a traditional survey of a 1 HA site would include approx. 300 data points, whereas the Sitemark solution can offer 20 million or more data points for the customer. This makes complex calculations like volume, depth, surface anomalies or object calculations significantly more accurate. Furthermore, having a digitized and visual record of the digital twin over allows for other possibilities such as calculating changes over time, measuring degradation or improvements over time among other things. At the same time, this new approach also has its own limitations, for instance the purpose of the technology is not to replace the need for human surveys on site, Sitemark's technology enables a significantly more precise overall survey/inspection of the entire site, which otherwise would be financially impossible, unsafe or take significant amount of time. Such a survey would then identify areas of human onsite interventions and inspections, hence making both approaches complementary to each other and as result able to provide better coverage of the entire site. The mining site inspection costs would be significantly reduced using the Sitemark platform solution, which can be complemented with more precise human onsite inspections and interventions where relevant. It also would provide a significantly improved coverage of the site and improve onsite safety by measuring damage or degradation among others.

The Goldeneye project will combine a multitude of drone carried sensors such as IR, RGB, multispectral and EM sensors in a user-friendly visual manner to provide relevant information for mine operators. The project will use drone-based imagery from selected targets to calibrate satellite spectral data, where existing airborne geophysical (magnetic, electromagnetic & radiometric) data are used as additional information and magnetic surveying is used to provide data from selected targets if needed.

Electromagnetic (EM) measurements are one of the main methods of applied geophysics used in mineral exploration, geological mapping and environmental studies. Most existing EM survey systems are ground systems, where transmitter and receiver are carried and operated by field personnel. Ground EM systems are effective in small areas that are accessible to humans. They have great depth of exploration, but they are very slow to perform compared to airborne surveys. Airborne surveys can either be manned airborne (helicopter and airplane) EM systems or drone-based systems. Manned airborne systems are suitable for mapping of very large areas. Even though their ground penetration is deeper, their operational costs are much higher than that of drone-based EM systems. A drone-based electromagnetic survey system provides a fast and cost-effective way to map the conductivity of soil and bedrock. This information is valuable for mineral exploration and environmental monitoring as well as in the urban planning and construction business sectors. Drones can fly safely over challenging areas that humans cannot enter, e.g. tailing areas or polluted areas. Applying drone technology, it is possible to conduct EM surveys, analyze the acquired data and obtain results quickly.

The Goldeneye project aims to develop a unique sensitive drone-based electromagnetic (EM) system for mapping subsurface soil and bedrock for environmental monitoring. In contrast with

existing single-drone survey systems that utilize either a local transmitter or distant EM sources, the project will use two drones to allow scaling the measurement frequency, loop separation and line spacing, which will result in optimal resolution and depth of investigation for each particular investigation problem. The first drone carries an EM transmitter and the second drone carries a 3-component induction coil receiver. Both drones are moving over the survey area in tandem or side by side with more-or-less fixed loop separation (the distance between the two drones). Unlike existing EM systems, there is no phase-link cable between the transmitter and receiver and the drones are free to change their relative orientation, position, and distance between each other during the measurement. With this new approach, the inversion of the parameters (layer conductivity and thickness) of 1D conductive-layered earth model is used to solve (apparent) conductivity/resistivity below the flight path. The inversion is made possible by accurate timing of the signals and measurement of the position (GPS), altitude and orientation of both drones. The results are presented as maps and pseudo-sections of apparent resistivity below the study area. One of the biggest challenges is to measure ultra-low signal levels under a noisy environment. To address this, the project will implement data analysis software for noise suppression (including induction effects arising from the moving and tilting transmitter loop and/or receiver coil). Currently, Radai is developing a drone-based electromagnetic survey system in an EU funded Horizon 2020 project New Exploration Technologies (NEXT) (2018–2021). The project aims to develop an EM survey system for mineral exploration with TRL 5. During the project, Radai has been developing and testing different kind of EM transmitters and receivers for drones. The experience and knowledge created in this project helps Radai to develop the unique two-drone system to create accurate geo-physical data for Goldeneye use cases. In addition, the Goldeneye project will develop a multispectral imaging system integrated with high-end magnetometer. Radai has been developing a drone based multispectral imaging system for mineral exploration in an EIT Raw Material project Multi Sensor Drone (2017 – 2020). The system has been tested in the Otanmäki mine and the Yara Finland mining site in Siilinjärvi and the experiences will support the development work in the Goldeneye project.

The integrated EM and multi-spectral system will be installed on an innovative drone survey platform, which consists of a rugged drone & accessories, custom sensors, survey planning software and data processing software. The drone is a high endurance fixed-wing plane (3m wingspan, 6kg payload) equipped with a fully autonomous autopilot, redundant telemetry communication links, a safety system and a data acquisition system. In this project, the drone platform will be improved further to fulfil international requirements for environmental and monitoring surveys, such as flight time, payload, redundant data acquisition techniques, high end battery efficiency and field operational safety measures. Photos and spectral imagery data obtained by satellites or drones “see” only the top surface of the earth. Measurements of geophysical (e.g. gravity, magnetic, electric or electromagnetic) fields, however, provide information from the subsurface and, thus, help interpret the true 3D geology of the target area. The project will use custom software from Radai (for geophysical analysis and post-processing of drone-based magnetic data) and Sitemark (for operational monitoring of the mine). The project will develop an effective and affordable platform for future system development - including interfaces to web services and data

sharing functionalities. The project will also record GNSS data in parallel to allow offline accurate positioning with sensor fusion and accurate timing – for better data analysis.

The project will define the data acquisition standards required during the course of the project for each mining application, which is crucial to the successful scale up and commercial deployment of the solution after project completion. For instance, flight altitudes, and acquisition standards may be different between an active mine and a post-closure mining site. These situations will inherently influence sensor setup and utilization, lens calibrations, flight height, flight speed, GSD (Ground Sampling Distance), image overlaps, utilization of GCPs (Ground Control Points), importance of terrain following during each flight etc. Once each of the use case configurations has been identified, they will be loaded onto the drone controller app or defined into the hardware and sensor operations manually to make such inspections repeatable during the project and after the project on a commercial level for the industry. The project will therefore involve further development of Sitemark's aerial data platform (already used in energy, construction, agriculture and basic mining and quarrying operations) so that it can support new advanced mining applications.

The Goldeneye acquisition and processing methods will enable mining operators to improve risk management, using the fusion of satellites, drone and proximal sensors to increase mine safety, community confidence and environmental outcomes.

Sitemark NV has been developing an aerial data platform for the past 3 years and in a number of grants. The ones which are relevant for this project are:

H2020-SC5-2016-2017-SEP-210405754 (MONOCLE): The overarching vision for MONOCLE is to create stronger ties between Earth Observation (EO) and in situ observation of water quality in remote locations. With this innovation, Sitemark's automated system could be deployed around remote lakes around the world to monitor health of the lake and capture other relevant ambient data with the use of sensors mounted on the drone and charging station.

H2020-SMEInst-2018-2020-2-829384, Sitemark was awarded the European innovation project Vertical Infrastructures. The overarching vision for the project is to further develop and commercialize the PoCs that was built as part Vlaio Innovation Project HBC.2017.0711 and deploy it on a European scale as to become the major European player.

Vlaio/KMO Project (HBC.2019.2115): Project aimed at developing the necessary foundation algorithms for improving accuracy, image processing and data analytics for this H2020 project.

Figure 4. Sitemark platform a) Automatically calculates the volume of stockpile based on the circled area, b) Automatically calculates the gradient/slope of the access roads.

3.2.1. KPIs and technological performance indicators of drone-based mining site monitoring

The drone imaging processing platform together with the aerial data acquisition could help reduce the drilling costs of the mines by improving the recognition of locations containing possible valuable minerals (KPI 1) even up to 20-40%. The EM measurement system provides a fast way to measure soil and bedrock conductivity, which in turn indicates the different consistencies of the ground beneath the surface. The technology is environmentally friendly, since it is contact-free and thus does not affect the environment under survey (KPI 2). Sitemark expects to decrease environmental impact by 10~20% by using the new platform as it enables quick coverage of a target area and reduces the need for invasive mineral exploration focusing efforts to the most interesting areas around the mining sites. Sitemark also expects to create 5-20 new jobs over the course of 5 years due to expanding the company expertise into the area of mining site monitoring (KPI 5). The platform is expected to improve the resolution of elevation maps from two to three fold (2x-3x, KPI 8). In addition, using drone-based monitoring with integrated EM and multispectral imaging systems will enable the detection of changes in the environment of the mining site and discover polluted areas (KPI 10 and 11). Drones are highly effective for such monitoring as they can cover large areas including parts, where humans have trouble entering with survey equipment. There will be scientific papers published during the project to spread out information and show the possibilities of the EM survey system as a new way to perform environmental monitoring and mineral exploration (KPI 9). Sitemark will create new services with possible focus on mineral detection, safety, geo-hazards, environmental monitoring and operations management as well as within construction and infrastructure monitoring industries.

Table 2. Indication of relevant Key performance indicators for Fuse Platform and aerial mine site monitoring using EM and multispectral sensors.

<i>KPI description</i>	<i>KPI no</i>	<i>EM survey</i>	<i>Multispectral</i>	<i>Fuse Platform</i>
Reduced drilling costs by 40%	1	✓		✓
Reduced environmental impact due to less immersive techniques	2	✓	✓	✓
New Sn, W, Sb, In, Cu and Au mineral deposits in Germany and Bulgaria	3			✓
Ge, Ga, In, Se, Te content in the run-of mine ore	4			
120 jobs over the next 5 years for consortium partners	5			✓
Net Present Value of Goldeneye investment between €2M and €29M per site over 5 years (depending on size)	6			
50% < Internal Rate of Return < 100% for all site operators over 5 years	7			
Production of 0.5m Digital Elevation Maps on weekly basis with <0.5m vertical accuracy (RMSE)	8			✓
At least 10 scientific publications, at least 2 educational courses (PDAC, IGC), at least 5 new patents filings	9	✓		
Reduced environmental impact due to less drilling required	10	✓		✓
Zero accident on mining sites protecting the community and the environment. Zero environmental pollution	11		✓	
At least 5 new Copernicus-derived services focusing on mineral detection, safety, geo-hazards, environmental monitoring and operations management	12			

3.3. Proximal data

One of the objectives of the Goldeneye project is to study the use of portable Raman spectroscopic analyser and Active Hyperspectral Spectrometer for mineral exploration and thus detection of valuable and secondary minerals in the mining sites. The conventional methods for the identification of minerals have been based on laboratory analyses such as Mineral Liberation Analysis (MLA) and Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) in addition to estimations made by the geologists on the appearance of the ore in rock surfaces and drill cores. The state-of-art technology today in spectral laboratory analyses is X-Ray Diffraction (XRD). The major issue in XRD as an onsite analyser or a process monitoring tool is that it requires extensive sample pretreatment. This sets requirements for an automated sampling solution with a preparation robot. The analysis time per sample in XRD devices is typically from 20 minutes to 1 hour. This is too slow for process control purposes, let alone for real-time analysis of rock surfaces. However, in recent decade different handheld and portable technologies have raised interest in the mining industry as they could provide information in real-time and would not cause delays in exploration and extraction surveys.

3.3.1. *Active hyperspectral sensing*

Hyperspectral imaging has been used in mineral exploration and other mining applications for decades. The conventional hyperspectral remote sensing uses sunlight as an illumination source, which restricts its application to sunny days and open-pit mining. In underground mining, only extremely short-distance hyperspectral sensing (up to about one meter) is possible using active illumination with halogen bulbs or LED arrays. One way to address these limitations is the application of camera systems based on pulsed lasers as a light source[12]. However, such systems use monochromatic light and do not provide spectral information of the imaged target.

Active hyperspectral sensing (AHS) has been developed recently[13,14]. This approach is based on supercontinuum light sources. Thus, it allows obtaining spectral information in a wide range of wavelengths with longer detection distances. This approach has been studied previously for mining sector applications and has been shown to be useful for ore grade evaluation[15]. However, these devices only gather spectral data from a single spot and are not suitable for screening large areas. Thus, a combination of active supercontinuum illumination with hyperspectral imaging is lacking.

In the Goldeneye project, VTT will develop an active hyperspectral sensing system based on the combination of a supercontinuum light source combined with a hyperspectral imaging solution. Active sample surface illumination will be performed using a high-power broadband supercontinuum light source together with a smart light filtering approach based on MEMS Fabry-Pérot interferometers. On the other hand, imaging will be performed using a scanning mirror-based system. This combination of a supercontinuum light source with the imaging system is a key innovation for remote screening in mining applications. Such an approach will allow imaging with real-time minerals mapping and classification under any light conditions in a huge range of distances for underground and open-pit mining.

VTT has previous experience with the development of single spot based active hyperspectral sensors for real-time ore/gangue separation combined with multi-sensor positioning in the framework of Business Finland funded “Efficient & Safe Identification of Minerals: Smart Real-Time methods” project during the years 2016-2018.

3.3.2. *Time resolved Raman spectroscopy*

Raman spectroscopy (RS) is a technology based on the vibration of molecule bonds of material and characterisation of material through detection of emitted (Raman scattered) photons. Although Raman scattering is a weak phenomenon, powerful laser excitation can be used to produce enough scattering so that a material spectrum can be recorded. In Raman measurement, the collected

¹² Christnacher, et al., Influence of gating and of the gate shape on the penetration capacity of range-gated active imaging in scattering environments, *Opt. Express*, 2015, 23 (26), pp. 32897-32908.

¹³ Manninen, et al., Long distance active hyperspectral sensing using high-power near-infrared supercontinuum light source, *Opt. Express*, 2014, 22 (6), pp. 7172-7177.

¹⁴ Kääriäinen, et al., Active Hyperspectral Sensor Based on MEMS Fabry-Pérot Interferometer, *Sensors*, 2019, 19 (9), 2192.

¹⁵ Jaanson, et al. A continuously tunable NIR laser and its applications in material classification, 2018, *Proceedings of SPIE Remote Sensing: Lidar Technologies, Techniques, and Measurements for Atmospheric Remote Sensing XIV*, September 10-13, 2018, 1079107.

inelastic photons form a spectrum – a Raman spectrum, which provides a fast and easy-to-use way to identify unknown minerals and to quantify their concentrations. First commercial Raman instrument was introduced in 1953, making Raman spectroscopy available to a wider audience. Today there exist over 30 companies providing different type of Raman devices from hand-held systems to large high-performance units with special microscopic sampling platforms. Still the use of this technique is mainly focused on material research and scientific use.

The prior use of RS for mineralogical analysis has been made with bench-top devices and it shows that Raman scattering can differentiate a large amount of minerals from each other[16,17,18,19]. The mineralogical Raman analysis can utilise a global digitalization project RRUFF (<http://rruff.info/>), which provides free access to large mineral spectral database containing the Raman spectra of approximately 3,500 different mineral species.

Thus, Raman spectroscopy could be an ideal tool for the on-site analysis of minerals, as it is fast, does not require sample pre-treatment, and is non-destructive as well as easy to use even by non-professionals. However, conventional Raman spectroscopy has a major drawback; fluorescence emission of ore can overlap the Raman signal in the measured spectra, making the identification or quantification of materials impossible. The most common way to try to avoid fluorescence during Raman measurement is to use longer wavelength excitation. However, a significant amount of Raman scattering is lost when longer excitation wavelengths are used, leading to poor signal-to-noise ratio in spectra, lower sensitivity and considerably longer measurement times. Fluorescence emission is therefore a serious limitation especially with mineralogical analysis.

Time resolved Raman offers a possible solution for this challenge. This technology is based on different lifetimes of the Raman scattering and fluorescence emission. Raman scattering occurs within a few picoseconds of the laser excitation, whereas fluorescence emission has longer decay time. The project innovation will use time-resolved Raman measurement, where this time difference can be used for the separation of these two phenomena, and the suppression of the fluorescence. In contrast with costly solutions based on Kerr gating[20] or ICCD camera electrical gating[21], the solution will use cost-effective SPAD[22] (Single Photon Avalanche Diode) array detectors. The resulting time-gated Raman spectrometer will be capable of overcoming fluorescence interferences (time domain-based fluorescence suppression) when the fluorescence

¹⁶ S. Das, M. J. Hendry, *Chem. Geol.* 2011, 290, 101.

¹⁷ R. Frost, T. Kloprogge, J. Schmidt, *Internet J. Vib. Spectrosc.* 1999, 3, 2.

¹⁸ M. Secchi, M. Zanatta, E. Borovin, M. Bortolotti, A. Kumar, M. Giarola, A. Sanson, B. Orberger, N. Daldosso, S. Gialanella, G. Mariotto, M. Montagna, L. Lutterotti, *J. Raman Spectrosc* 2018, 49, 1023.

¹⁹ T. Dörfer, W. Schumacher, N. Tarcea, M. Schmitt, J. Popp, *J. Raman Spectrosc* 2009, 41, 684.

²⁰ Coates et al., Picosecond Time-Resolved Resonance Raman Probing of the Light-Switch States of [Ru(Phen)₂dppz]²⁺, *J. Phys. Chem. B*, 2001, 105 (50), pp 12653–12664.

²¹ Efremov et al., Fluorescence Rejection in Resonance Raman Spectroscopy Using a Picosecond-Gated Intensified Charge-Coupled Device Camera, *Appl.Spectrosc.*, 2007, 61, (6), pp. 571-578 (2007)

²² Nissinen, et al., 2x(4x)128 Time-gated CMOS Single Photon Avalanche Diode Line Detector with 100 ps Resolution for Raman Spectroscopy, 2013, Proceedings of 39th European Solid-State Circuits Conference (ESSCIRC), September 16-20, 2013, Bukarest, Romania, pp. 291-294.

decay times of samples are > 300 ps. In the case of mineral samples, fluorescence decay times are typically several nanoseconds, which allows complete time-based fluorescence suppression.

Figure 5. Benefit of time resolved Raman spectroscopy in suppressing the mineral fluorescence emission.

The concept of time resolved Raman spectroscopy has been originally developed together by the Optical Measurement team from VTT, Optical Research Centre from Tampere University and Oulu University Electrical Engineering laboratory. The technology was commercialised in 2014 by a new company Timegate Instruments Ltd, which is continuing to drive the technological development further. Timegate instrument's technological asset is based on the company's own IC designs of CMOS-SPAD of detector arrays, as there are no commercial options available for Raman spectroscopy applications. Timegate is the first and so far the only company that has had the capability to bring this solution to the market. There have been other similar trials in Europe, Asia and USA, but from these efforts, no technical or commercial breakthrough has been seen for now. E.g. NASA has developed similar time-gated system to be sent to MARS to identify minerals there. If we compare the performance of our system with NASA's system, the gating time in our current detector is nearly 10 times faster than NASA's detector design thus allowing us better fluorescence rejection. Furthermore, we have also been faster in IPR protection and got granted patent families for the unique detector technology, and therefore NASA's patent application has not been granted.

In mining industry, Timegate Instruments taken part in the studies on Timegated[®]Raman technology for flotation process monitoring and laboratory validation of the samples taken from the flotation process. In concentration plants, the technology allows the monitoring of the changes in the mineral concentrations and compositions from the processed material streams straight from the pipes (slurries) and from the conveyor belts (powders). TG Raman gives information about the properties of the ore in real-time (in seconds/minutes response time) preventing the process control delays and profit losses that happen with existing material analysis techniques based on sampling and lab analyses.

The optical measurement team at VTT has since continued to study the applicability of the technology in collaboration with Timegate Instruments in different industrial processes including mineral characterisation for mining industry and metal processing. Business Finland funded 3DLIDAR project and EIT Raw Materials funded T-REX project both are developing new Raman probe solutions to mineral characterisations. 3DLIDAR project has focus in metal processing industry and T-REX project is focussed on drill core analysis in a data fusion with other technologies including

laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy and XRF. In T-REX the target is to integrate the technology into the drilling core scanner device developed by German based company DMT. These projects are increasing the knowledge on the benefits of time-gated Raman in mineralogical predictions.

In addition, compared to the conventional Raman technology, the time-resolved Raman is significantly less sensitive to ambient light and thermal emissions. Thus, it is more suitable for studying high temperature samples in industrial fabrication processes such as calcination for Spodumene conversion. Spodumene is the main mineral containing lithium and thus a critical mineral for the battery industry. The performance of time resolved Raman for high-thermal calcination process monitoring has been studied in a Business Finland funded Opti-Hai project. The project showed that TG Raman could monitor the lithium conversion process from α -form, which cannot be leached efficiently, into the tetragonal β -form during the heat treatment process. Unlike other spectroscopic methods, time-gated Raman is suitable for process monitoring in extremely harsh ambient temperatures.

Raman spectroscopy has been applied as a research tool for the characterisation of minerals in laboratories for decades. However, it has not been applied commonly as an onsite tool, because it has had challenges with size, cost and range of minerals suitable for analysis due to fluorescence issues. The need for fast onsite analysis has been recognised in the mining industry and there are technologies, which have been gaining interest as fast analysis tools. These include hand-held X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) and Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy (LIBS) devices, which give information on the material elements. Although, the development of XRF and LIBS for on-site tools especially in drill core and sorting analysis is ongoing, there are challenges with these technologies. Both XRF and LIBS provide elemental information of the ore components and do not reveal the exact minerals present in the ore. The recorded data gives indication on minerals, but the challenge is that many minerals consist of similar elemental compositions. Thus, these technologies require a priori information on the geology of the mining sites and rely on successful calibration of the mineral estimation algorithms. Hand-held XRF is also limited to heavy elements and cannot distinguish light elements such as sulphur, which are common in many minerals. Thus, even if the supporting information is available, the mineral estimations can have challenges with accuracy. On the other hand, the LIBS technology can distinguish a wider amount of elements, but it is destructive as it needs a plasma arc in order distinguish the material elements between the sensor and the material. The benefits of hand-held XRF and LIBS compared to current Raman devices suitable for mineral analysis include affordable price, compact size and fast measurements. However, XRF and LIBS still often require sample pre-treatment and additional lab testing to confirm the mineral predictions. The KPIs of competing technologies and Raman spectroscopy are the same, but the performance level can be lower due to elemental information, need for a priori-information and limited element range. The benefit of Raman spectroscopy is that it provides information on the minerals themselves instead of the mere elements. It is also not limited by the weight of the elements. On the other hand, Raman spectroscopy is still less developed as an onsite tool, the technology is more expensive with large equipment size and slower measurement times compared to XRF and LIBS.

Table 3. Comparison of current TG Raman and handheld XRF and LIBS devices for onsite mineral analysis.

Technology	Size	Price range	Information	Material	Measurement time
TG Raman	Bench-top/portable	Price level < 100 k€	Mineralogical	Wide variety of minerals	Ten seconds - minutes
XRF	Hand-held	Price level < 50 k€	Elemental	Heavy elements	Seconds
LIBS	Hand-held	Price level < 50 k€	Elemental	Wide variety of elements	Seconds

3.3.3. KPIs and technological performance indicators for the proximity sensors

Active hyperspectral imaging provides spectral-based mineral classification under any light conditions in a huge range of distances meeting the KPIs number 3 and 4 for mineral analysis. It is a real-time method to obtain information about minerals distribution on the rock surface without any immersive steps (KPI 2). The information provided about mineral distribution on the rock surfaces helps to define the area for drilling applications more precisely, reducing the environmental impact (KPI 10). The development for AHS for mine site mineralogical analysis will be published in a peer-reviewed journal to inform the scientific community on the advantages of AHS in mineral classification (KPI 9).

Raman spectroscopy is a pointwise measurement and cannot map large ground areas in high resolution on its own although it allows onsite mineralogical analysis (KPI 3-4). The amount of sample spots is limited and, thus, Raman spectroscopy acts as a complementary method to other EOD technologies. In Goldeneye project, Raman spectroscopy will be used to calibrate the EOD mapping methods and improve the accuracy of EOD mineralogical area predictions. This can reduce the number of areas needed to drill for finding new mineral deposits in exploration of the mining sites (KPI 1). In addition, Raman spectroscopy can also improve the knowledge of the mining site mineralogy and reduce unnecessary extraction of ore as well as focus the core drilling to right locations eluding unnecessary drilling and blasting (KPI 2). The combination of Raman spectroscopy as a mineralogical on-site tool together with EOD can help in improving the profitability of mines through recognition of areas with valuable mineral deposits as well as better knowledge of the ore consistency in extraction and improved ore processing. This can have positive effect on the employment situation of the mines (KPI 5-7) as well as reduce the environmental effect (KPI 10). The achieved improvement in mineralogical prediction will be published in a peer-reviewed journal (KPI 9).

Sandvik (SMC) and Timegate Instruments will develop a proximal sensing solution for onsite mineral detection based on time-gated Raman spectroscopy (KPI 3, 4). The Raman spectrometer will be

integrated in a drilling unit to analyse the mineral content of the drilled material on the go. The real-time mineralogical information can help reduce the need for additional drilling and thus also reduce the overall drilling costs (KPI 1, 2, 10). The analysis result will be sent to the Golden AI platform, where the data will be used to augment the mineral predictive maps produced by other Goldeneye sensing methods.

The indicators of performance for the proximity sensing:

- The sensitivity reached at the field trials sites in day light conditions (limit of detection for different valuable minerals): input from mines on the concentration levels they would need to distinguish.
- Variety and amount of detected minerals (different minerals detected and identified).
- Increased prediction accuracy of EOD mapping: input needed from WP2 on the current level and desired level.

Table 4. Indication of relevant key performance indicators for mineralogical analysis using proximity sensors.

<i>KPI description</i>	<i>KPI no</i>	<i>TG Raman in field analysis</i>	<i>TG Raman integrated in drilling unit</i>	<i>Active Hyperspectral sensing</i>
Reduced drilling costs by 40%	1	✓	✓	
Reduced environmental impact due to less immersive techniques	2	✓	✓	✓
New Sn, W, Sb, In, Cu and Au mineral deposits in Germany and Bulgaria	3	✓		✓
Ge, Ga, In, Se, Te content in the run-of mine ore	4	✓	✓	✓
120 jobs over the next 5 years for consortium partners	5	✓		
Net Present Value of Goldeneye investment between €2M and €29M per site over 5 years (depending on size)	6	✓	✓	
50% < Internal Rate of Return < 100% for all site operators over 5 years	7	✓	✓	
Production of 0.5m Digital Elevation Maps on weekly basis with <0.5m vertical accuracy (RMSE)	8			
At least 10 scientific publications, at least 2 educational courses (PDAC, IGC), at least 5 new patents filings	9	✓	✓	✓
Reduced environmental impact due to less drilling required	10	✓	✓	✓
Zero accident on mining sites protecting the community and the environment. Zero environmental pollution	11			
At least 5 new Copernicus-derived services focusing on mineral detection, safety, geo-hazards, environmental monitoring and operations management	12			

3.4. GNSS positioning

The creation of mineralogical prediction maps integrating EOD data with drone data as well as onsite sensor data requires accurate knowledge of the location of the recorded data during the detection. This affects the mapping results and in worst case can give incorrect indications for example on the locations of the valuable mineral deposits. If a drone flown sensor indicates the area 100 meters off the actual position, this can cause extensive drilling costs to the mining company without any successful results. Similarly, the indoor positioning in an underground mine needs to be accurate (or repeatable in some cases) to give a realistic view into the mining activities as well as the locations on the surface of the mine. Inaccurate positioning can have serious consequences into the mine stability or tailings stability on the surface of the ground. This is why Goldeneye project will address both outdoor as well as indoor positioning challenges.

3.4.1. Indoor Navigation with micro-simulators

Unlike commonly used GNSS solutions (which work mostly outdoor) and wireless beacon technologies (which work mostly indoor), the Goldeneye project will provide high accuracy geolocation capabilities indoor and outdoor using novel GNSS micro-simulators from partner GSN. The micro simulator is a device that has a multichannel GNSS transmitter, that are able to replicate GNSS satellite signals as it would have been received at that point if not for the blockage (roof or other) of the satellite signals. The simulator can force the receiver to be at any position – in our system it forces the receiver to be on the right position.

The indoor system Includes:

External antenna that received the outdoor GPS signals and allows full synchronization between the indoor system and the outdoor system.

Central unit the heart of the system is a 3U box that can support up to 36 micro simulators synchronizes to the external GPS system with optical transmission output.

Optic to RF units – passive translator

This approach is different from pseudolites (pseudo-satellites), which create a local terrestrial constellation of satellites, but require special non-standard GNSS receiver and suffer from positioning inaccuracy caused from signal multipath. The solution will be deployed in the underground mining scenario (field trials 4 in Pyhäsalmi, Finland).

Table 5. Comparison table of different indoor positioning technologies.

	Technique	Algorithm	Accuracy	Cost	Complexity	Scalability	Privacy /Security	Real Time
Infrared	Trilateration	TOA/TDOA	Medium	High	High	Medium	Low	Yes
Magnetic	Triangulation	AOA/TOA	High	High	High	Low	Low	Yes
Optical/ Vision	Scene A.	-	Low	Medium	Medium	Low	Low	Yes
Audible Sound	Triangulation	AOA/TOA	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low	Yes
Ultrasound/Sonic								
Active Bat	Trilateration	TOA/TDOA	Medium	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low	Yes
Cricket	Triangulation	AOA/TOA	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium	Yes
Dolphin	Trilateration	TOA/TDOA	Medium	Low	Medium	Medium	Low	Yes

Radio Frequency									
Bluetooth	Scene A.	RSSI	Low	High	Medium	Medium	Low	Yes	
UWB	Trilateration	TOA/TDOA	High	Medium	Medium	High	Low	Yes	
Sensor Networks	Scene A.	RSSI	Low	Medium	Medium	Medium	Low	Yes	
WLAN	Scene A.	RSSI	Low	Medium	High	Medium	Low	Yes	
RFID	Scene A.	RSSI	Low	Medium	Medium	High	Low	Yes	
NFC	Proximity	-	High	Low	Low	High	High	No	
GSN	Triangulation	TDOA/ RSSI	High	Low	Medium	High	Very high	Yes	

The underground testing environment benefits significantly from the underground geolocation by GNSS. It enables easily compatible tracking, mapping and location-specific data production of vehicles and devices. Modern vehicle tracking systems commonly use GPS technology. Thus, conventional vehicle tracking systems may be integrated into the monitoring of conditions, operations and movement in underground test sites.

The indoor GNSS system includes external antenna that receives the outdoor GPS signals and allows full synchronization between the indoor system and the outdoor system. The system has a management unit, which connects software GNSS Receiver to an external antenna located outside the building. The software receiver collects the ephemerides data from the satellites and synchronizes the time of the indoor system to the time of the outdoor satellite system to allow a smooth transition between outdoor and indoor. The timing utilises an accurate clock (OCXO or atomic clock), which is controlled by the software receiver. The system uses a broadcasting manager, which decides the constellation (a set of satellites) that will broadcast to each antenna, timing to compensate for various delays in the system as well as the transmitting power level of each satellite at each antenna (output). Baseband Unit (FPGA function) produces the baseband signal for the 36 antennas of the system. For optical signal transmittance, there are six optical transmitters units; each unit consists of 6 sub-units. Each sub-unit receives from the baseband signal for transmission.

Figure 6. The indoor system description for mining operations in underground mines.

The indoor GNSS navigation technology, which will be further developed in Goldeneye-project for underground mine positioning, has been tested in several POCs including a paid POC with Corning, GSN offices and AT&T offices in Israel. GSN has installed this system in a building located in the airport city, Israel for indoor navigation for pedestrians. In this system, a Corning active high-end DAS has been used as a transmitting units.

Figure 7. Image showing the pedestrian movement between different floors inside the airport facilities

3.4.2. GPS/Galileo Software receiver

The project will implement software based GNSS receivers from GSN for sensors to be tracked. Software GNSS receivers require fewer hardware components and offer greater flexibility compared to traditional receivers whose correlators and accumulators are implemented in dedicated integrated circuit hardware. The software-based GNSS receiver will allow mining equipment operators to easily add full GNSS functionality with design flexibility and long-term upgradeability at a minimal cost, low power, and no physical size to today's cost-sensitive IoT applications. GSN will accelerate the performance of its GNSS software receiver by creating several custom instructions to run on DSP. This will enable the GNSS software to require less than 110 MHz for full 12-satellite functionality. We will integrate the novel GNSS sensors on drones and ground sensors used in the project. This will provide better accuracy, better stability and better sensitivity to the positioning of these assets. The project will develop novel applications of Earth observation and Earth GNSS data acquisition and processing for the mining industry.

3.4.3. Outdoor Navigation with PPP

PPP is an outdoor accurate positioning technique utilising GNSS. It is capable of providing positioning solutions at centimetre to decimetres level by combining precise satellite positions and clocks with un-differenced, dual-frequency (to remove the first order effect of the ionosphere), pseudo-range and carrier-phase GNSS observables. In static mode, PPP can provide even sub-centimetre positioning precision. PPP differs from traditional Double-Difference (DD) relative baseline positioning (e.g., Real Time Kinematics, RTK) in the sense that it does not require access to simultaneous observations from one or more close reference stations for accurate survey. As a result, PPP provides absolute positioning information, contrarily to RTK, which instead provides relative positioning information with respect to a reference station. PPP requires precise orbit and clock data, which are computed by a processing centre with measurements coming from reference stations belonging to a relatively sparse network (i.e., thousands of km apart would suffice). This

makes PPP a very attractive alternative to RTK for those areas where RTK coverage is limited or not available.

One of the main drawbacks of PPP techniques is that they require a long convergence time to achieve the utmost performance. Standard PPP techniques generally take tens of minutes to start converging. However, novel PPP techniques recently proposed are capable to reduce this initial convergence time (e.g., down to approx. 10-15 minutes).

Eli (GSN CEO) has applied an Azimuth Detering System (ADS) in the past – using Double Difference with two antennas at distance of 1 meter with better than 3 mill-radian accuracy. In Goldeneye-project, GNS will use off-the-shelf low cost Multi bands Multi systems GNSS receivers (price some hundreds of dollars per receiver). They will be integrated with open source PPP software to get an inexpensive system with target accuracy of about 10 cm. The system will also include a communication system to get the data needed from the reference station network. It should be noted that the nature of the antenna is an important parameter of the system - GNS will search for an antenna that combines a reasonable price with a reasonable quality.

One of the advantages of the PPP techniques is that the PPP will lower the cost and complexity of the operations (will allow for less professional staffing). Today classic RTK measurements require equipment that cost 20,000-40,000 Euros. The high price reduces the use of RTK measurements, lowering the price will allow for widespread use and fix installation of more vehicles on a regular basis.

3.4.4. KPIs and technological performance indicators for the GNSS systems

The outdoor positioning system with PPP will offer new solutions for low cost, independent (no need for reference station) and accurate positioning of mining operations. This has the potential to reduce unnecessary drillings in exploration and extraction (KPI 1). The PPP system can open new business opportunities for GSN as well as new system solutions for other project members (KPI 5-7). In addition, opening of the Mining Market to Indoor Navigation Systems and the ability to view and demonstrate the system during the project will induce growth to the GSN employee amount. Successful collaboration with the companies that provide consortium mines can also bring significant growth (KPI 5-7) as the system helps optimizing the mine workflow. This can increase employee productivity, manageability and efficient utilization of heavy mechanical tools. Accurate indoor navigation can ensure better security in preventing accidents and better worker position as well as status (moving or static) in case of an accident (KPI 11). GNS is planning to write a journal paper on indoor navigation in underground mine together with Oulu University (KPI 9).

Table 6. Indication of relevant key performance indicators for indoor navigation and PPP outdoor navigation systems.

KPI description	KPI no	Indoor Navigation	PPP outdoor navigation
Reduced drilling costs by 40%	1		✓
Reduced environmental impact due to less immersive techniques	2		
New Sn, W, Sb, In, Cu and Au mineral deposits in Germany and Bulgaria	3		
Ge, Ga, In, Se, Te content in the run-of mine ore	4		
120 jobs over the next 5 years for consortium partners	5	✓	✓
Net Present Value of Goldeneye investment between €2M and €29M per site over 5 years (depending on size)	6	✓	✓
50% < Internal Rate of Return < 100% for all site operators over 5 years	7	✓	✓
Production of 0.5m Digital Elevation Maps on weekly basis with <0.5m vertical accuracy (RMSE)	8		✓
At least 10 scientific publications, at least 2 educational courses (PDAC, IGC), at least 5 new patents filings	9	✓	✓
Reduced environmental impact due to less drilling required	10		
Zero accident on mining sites protecting the community and the environment. Zero environmental pollution	11	✓	
At least 5 new Copernicus-derived services focusing on mineral detection, safety, geo-hazards, environmental monitoring and operations management	12		

4. Golden AI demonstrator – heterogeneous Data Fusion and AI platform

Satellites, Drones and Aerial surveys are becoming more common on mining sites today. As this data is captured in the form of images, there are challenges in timely and fast managing and analysis of such data amounts. Additionally, making sense of data produced with variety of different sensors and being able to work with multiple types of data sets (whether it is RGB, Electromagnetic (EM), thermal or multispectral) increases the degree of complexity and the amount of challenges. The aim of Goldeneye project is to create a platform to merge the available information, create more value through the results and simplify the user experience.

The Goldeneye project will enable novel uses of Earth observation and Earth GNSS data in the mining industry by integrating third-party and in-situ data that can enrich the data from Copernicus services into data fusion and AI platform. For example, aerial drone data and in-situ sensor data will be used for the calibration of the Copernicus satellites in the context of mining exploration, extraction or closure. The resulting models and high-resolution maps will enhance the capabilities of European (and global) mining operators. Currently, in the mining sector AI is minimally used outside applications where Machine Learning methods are applied.

For The Goldeneye project, consortium will deliver a complete integrated AI engine/platform, fusing all data such as:

- Integrate sensing data from satellites, drones and in-situ sensors for mineral detection, safety, geo-hazard, environmental monitoring and operations monitoring
- Integrate GNSS simulators and receivers
- Implement applications related exploration, extraction and closure / post closure scenarios
- Multi-sensor data integration software
- Data fusion workflows and tools
- Predictive software for mineral potential prediction during exploration
- Safety, geo-hazard and environmental monitoring applications
- Operational monitoring applications

Data fusion is used for combining information from two or more satellites or local/in-situ sensors monitoring the same land surface. Data fusion can be applied in the case where two satellites provide information on the same area with similar resolutions (e.g. Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2) to provide higher quality information. Data fusion can also be applied to the case where two satellites provide information in different spatial and temporal resolutions, in order to increase the temporal

resolution of high-resolution low-frequency satellite data with high-frequency low-resolution data. Furthermore, data fusion is applied, where satellite information can be linked with other datasets, such as multisensor geophysical datasets from drones. Using machine learning techniques, the surface information from the satellites can be fused with the surface geophysical information from the drones in 2D and then used to interpolate/ predict 3D spectral data into depth (below surface) based on available 3D geophysical data, without having the spectral data from the satellites continuing into the depth (below surface).

During the scope of the Goldeneye project, consortium will deploy the Golden AI product (the derivative name from Goldeneye project) system that merges satellite, drone and in-situ data captured into Goldeneye platform combined with a set of existing and newly developed data processing and AI algorithms that are able to calculate various aspects of the mining site such as slopes, bench heights, generate annotations around exceptions and anomalies.

During the Goldeneye project, Sitemark will develop collaborative tools where relevant users are able to collaborate and work in new innovative digital setup. This new solution of first digitizing the mining site and then working in a virtual setup to analyse the mining sites will be a game changer solution within and for the industry

The fused data products of the Golden AI demonstrator platform outputs will be added to a stack of generated ARD in ESA Data Cube facility for reuse.

EO satellites provide enormous amounts of 2D and 3D time series describing atmospheric and surface conditions over land and sea on a continuous basis, but only less than 5% of collected data is analysed by human analysts. The amount of EOD gathered by programmes such as Copernicus (already 20x larger than what can be processed by human analysts) will continue to grow with the proliferation of low-cost nano-satellites and commercial EO satellite constellations. Researchers have started to use statistical machine learning methods, also called artificial intelligence methods, to lower the burden of human analysts and automate the analysis of satellite data. These methods currently treat the way in which the data were generated or relationships between the variables as unknown. However, the existence of spatial relationships in satellite images is known, and an emerging way of modelling these relationships is to adapt existing machine learning algorithms proven to be effective for analysing these types of data. The Golden AI demonstrator platform has AI capabilities permitting the detection of patterns in large amounts of data, and flagging them for review by human analysts, according to the requirement of specific use-cases.

The anomaly detection method starts with automatic AI-powered feature selection in several steps:

Data collection: acquisition of raw (time-stamped) data, originating from logs, performance indicators, sensor measurements, multiband satellite imaging products, etc.

Data annotation: each event is characterized by a “severity score” (likelihood that the event is part of an anomaly or contains an anomalous divergence) calculated by a decoder model. The purpose

of decoder model is to provide the calculation methods and system of references for AI to correctly map deviation scores of various observed features according to each particular use case in question.

Data grouping: events are grouped together into event groups, containing consecutive events of the same type.

Anomaly triggers: the AI raises an alarm over an event group if the compounded parameter of severity per time interval (i.e. the summed severity of all events in that interval) fluctuates significantly over time. Uncorrelated features are determined and extracted at this stage for each alarm candidate.

Anomaly grouping: Similar alarms are grouped together in alarm groups, based on the severity scores of the events inside the alarms. Feature selection is based on providing the best information for machine learning algorithms (using all attributes is not optimal due to performance limitations and complexity of EOD source data).

Anomaly mining: anomaly groups are refined based on features extracted from the complex raw datasets. When initial set of anomalies is detected, the right attributes are chosen, some will not be in a numeric format, and will need a transformation step to make it possible to feed them into the machine learning algorithms.

This method substantially reduces the workload of human analysts as they are required only to analyse anomaly groups, and not individual events. After the features are selected or created, the data needs to be prepared. Here the clean-up and transformation of the data to the right format occurs in preparation for the machine learning. Used procedures, such as whitening (transforming the dataset to zero mean and unit variance) and PCA (dimensionality reduction), rely on a dataset to fit their parameters. This component produces the dataset used by the clusterer and classifier in the later stages.

The proposed solution uses an unsupervised K-means clustering method. This method tries to deduce information about each detected anomaly group, based on statistics showing the uniformity of the anomaly distribution within the group. This information is stored to assist the human expert when assessing and re-labelling/annotating the anomalies. The clustering method trains and optimizes its parameters the first time it is run, therefore it will be able to quickly cluster new similar anomalies as belonging to a known alarm group, or else creating a new anomaly group. The described process is based on the issued European patent of OPT and lays the foundation for the creation of the new AI instructions sets, also known as AI Knowledge packs – an innovative approach pioneered by OPT/NET.

In the past, OPT/NET has developed a multifunctional data platform to analyse geospatial data provided by satellites and to monitor in-situ sensor data streams at the same time. This platform will be utilised in the development of Golden AI demonstrator platform. In addition, two AI building blocks developed by OPT/NET in previous development projects (OptOSS AI and TSAR AI) will be used in the Goldeneye project to provide the basis for Golden AI platform.

Table 7. OPT/NET development projects to build the basis for multifunctional data platform.

Technology	Previous projects
OptOSS AI anomaly detection engine	ESA SBIC 2016
TSAR AI anomaly detection engine	Copernicus Masters Incubation grant 2018
Multifunctional data fusion and AI analytics platform	MONITORED AI [ESA ARTES IAP, 2019-20]
OPT, European Patent EP3369231B1	ESA SBIC 2016, Copernicus Masters Incubation 2018

The Golden AI platform will also benefit from the development project of other project partners providing tools for the platform construction. These include technologies developed by Sinergise: EO data processing engine incorporated in Sentinel Hub, machine learning toolkit and specific environmental governance and enforcement services based on EO technologies, as well as InSAR processing software for ground deformation by Dares Technology, Mineral prediction mapping software by Beak Consultants and drone data processing platform by Sitemark (Chapter 2.2).

Table 8. EU-funded research and development projects providing needed technological knowhow for the Golden AI platform construction.

Company	Technology	Previous projects
Sinergise	Satellite imagery processing in the cloud	H2020 EO VAS and openEO
Sinergise	Machine-learning technologies for Sentinel data	H2020 Perceptive Sentinel
Sinergise	Copernicus data to monitor environmental impact	H2020 EnviroLENS
DARES	InSAR processing software for ground deformation	H2020 MotionMapper
BEAK	Mineral prediction mapping software	H2020 NEXT
Sitemark	Earth Observation (EO) and in situ observation of water quality in remote locations	H2020 MONOCLE
Sitemark	Commercialization of PoCs built as part Vlaio Innovation Project	H2020-SMEInst Vertical Infrastructures
Sitemark	Development of algorithms for improving accuracy, image processing and data analytics	H2020 Vlaio/KMO Project

The development of the Goldeneye demonstrator platform (Golden AI) will follow user-centric by design augmented with “use case focused by design” principles. The overall project methodology will be based on agile development methods to bring flexibility and adaptability to the development process. This means that the development is overlapping with the field trials, in order to support iterative development. The solution will integrate AI-enabled processing platforms from various providers by utilising case-specific AI Knowledge Packs (AKPs).

EOS technology offers the advantages of providing almost every day LST of medium spatial resolution based on downscaling techniques. Currently, the alternative technologies used in the mining industry are based on Landsat 8 temperature maps. Although these technologies provide useful information, they have the limitations of 16-days’ time interval and cloud cover effect in sensing days. The EOS technology will downscale MOD11A1 to Landsat 8 spatial resolution providing dense time series of the Earth surface thermal observations.

Owing to Sentinel-2’s frequent revisit time, temporal series will allow a constant and regular monitoring of the mines’ surface properties, but also facilitate the detection of rapid changes

occurring to the mining facilities, thus enabling timely geotechnical responses, warning alert systems or environmental emergency decisions. The high spatial resolution of the instrument (10 and 20 m bands) has the potential for monitoring small-scale events within the open mines. Currently, the alternative technologies used in the mining industry are based on Landsat 8 optical images, or very-high-resolution images (VHR) provided by platforms such as Pleiades or SPOT. Although VHR images provide detailed maps with a resolution up to 50cm, the images are costly and often limited in the number of optical bands. Landsat-8 OLI has shown a robust performance for ore exploration and mine waste monitoring, however the instrument has a lower resolution (30m) than Sentinel-2 and a longer revisit-time of 16 days.

InSAR Technology is expected to have the advantages of obtaining reliable, accurate and frequent measurements of ground deformation. Currently the alternative/competing technologies used at mining industry are based in topography and in-situ instrumentation such as inclinometers.

Although these technologies provide useful information; they have the limitations of:

- They require installation and maintenance (i.e. prisms, inclinometers)
- In situ measurement devices are often damaged and measurements are lost
- Measurement results are limited to the in-situ devices. Poor density of measured points
- In-situ measurements are generally expensive and not very efficient in terms of volume of data

The proposed architecture of Golden AI demonstrator platform with AI Knowledge Packs (AKPs) is compatible and will be maintained as such in line with ESA vision for Common Architecture suite of projects and will be compatible with ESA Network of Resources (NoR). The exact technical specifications of such integration will be defined through the negotiations and collaboration with existing suppliers of ESA working on the implementation of these projects.

Machine Learning algorithms allow large amounts of reference points from images to be quickly collected for further precise stacking of the satellite images with precision exceeding 1/10 of the pixel size. The result of this process in Golden AI demonstrator platform is a multi-dimensional array (raster data or gridded data) referred to as Data Cube in this proposal. The Golden AI demonstrator platform presents the analysis ready data cubes to the users on a per-scene basis at present. The co-registered data of the Golden AI platform outputs will be added to a stack of generated ARD in the ESA Data Cube facility service for reuse. The resulting system will enable user access to the desired area of Earth surface on a per-pixel basis.

Figure 8. Example of ground subsidence measured over an underground salt mine in Spain with DARES technology.

Figure 7 shows an example of ground subsidence measured over an underground salt mine in Spain. Although mine excavation works occurs at 600 m of depth, important subsidence levels of 30 cm/year can be measured on the surface. Houses and small villages at the surrounding are presenting important cracks and in some cases are being evacuated.

Figure 9. An example of data processing workflow for forecasting of geo-hazards at the mining site (dam instabilities, soil subsidence, etc.) using time series and projected climate data together with remote sensing and drone monitoring data.

The benefit of the Golden AI platform demonstrator will be the ability of different users and stakeholders to visualize, work with, collaborate and report on various aspects of the mining site, such as asset tracking, automated calculation of stockpiles, detection of anomalies (e.g. conveyor belt mis-alignment, bearing overheating, damage detection, slope and bench calculations and anomalies, field validations). The applications will provide the following functionalities:

- Visualisation of the whole of mine site enabling more effective deployment of resources resulting an estimated 20% increase in resource utilisation.
- Accurate asset tracking of trucks and or other equipment currently in operation. Sensors mounted on such active assets will track crucial telemetry data across the mining site optimising asset utilisation, maintenance scheduling and onsite safety, reducing costs such as fuel and wear and tear on capital equipment by 10%. Inventory tracking and condition reporting is also an important requirement for closed mines to ensure overall safety, adherence to local and international environmental regulations and meeting community expectations.
- Automated sizing of stockpiles and active areas in operation enabling site measurement and calculation of volumes improving estimates of material on hand and improved forecasting. Three dimensional visualizations will inform more accurate fill and cut measurements across each of the sites. Automated reporting and alerts of stockpile changes can be provided, reducing the workload of human operators who can short to higher value tasks.
- Slope and bench calculations, anomaly identification and classification are crucial for the efficiency of operations utilizing trucks. Better slope design could lead to 15% reduction on fuel consumption and wear and tear on brakes and other elements of trucks which are a significant contributor to cost of operating a mine. As an active mining site's landscape is constantly evolving it is crucial that key elements such as slopes, haul way width, bench height and slopes are regularly monitored and controlled.

The Golden AI platform demonstrator will automate the recognition of known patterns in the fused data (EOD + drone data + in-situ data) through the creation of specific AI Knowledge Packs (AKPs) developed for each use case. Since known patterns will be recognised automatically, human analyst workload will decrease by a factor of 100x. Additionally, new and unknown patterns of significance will be autonomously detected and flagged for human attention, greatly reducing the time before high-quality assessment maps and reports become available to decision makers and users of the service. This can be particularly important for time-sensitive geohazard risk *management*. The solution is based on a technical layer consisting of backend Docker microservice execution with Kubernetes orchestration layer, API functions and operators, programming languages and toolkits, modules and libraries, cloud or hybrid computing platforms, data access platforms (DIAS platform and/or ESA Data Cube facility), AI-enabled processing platforms from various providers, use case-specific AI Knowledge Packs (AKPs). The proposed architecture is compatible and will be maintained as such in line with ESA vision for Common Architecture suite of projects and will be compatible with ESA Network of Resources (NoR). The exact technical specifications of such integration will be defined through the negotiations and collaboration with existing suppliers of ESA working on the implementation of these projects.

There is currently no competing AI platform for Golden AI capable of fusing and analyzing all sensor data including the satellite data, drone based data as well as proximity sensor data on one platform.

5. KPIs of the industry with focus on Goldeneye technologies

The Golden AI platform will fuse, analyse all time-series data from the partners involved, offering an unprecedented level of optimization for planning the test drilling areas as well as tools for better control of environmental impact of mines. In addition, The Golden AI platform offers the mines tools to reduce their operational costs as well as to optimize the used resources. The Key Performance Indicators defined by Goldeneye Grant Agreement are presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Description of Key Performance Indicators from Goldeneye Grant Agreement

KPI number	KPI description
1	Reduced drilling costs by 40%
2	Reduced environmental impact due to less immersive techniques
3	New Sn, W, Sb, In, Cu and Au mineral deposits in Germany and Bulgaria
4	Ge, Ga, In, Se, Te content in the run-of mine ore
5	120 jobs over the next 5 years for consortium partners
6	Net Present Value of Goldeneye investment between €2M and €29M per site over 5 years (depending on size)
7	50% < Internal Rate of Return < 100% for all site operators over 5 years
8	Production of 0.5m Digital Elevation Maps on weekly basis with <0.5m vertical accuracy (RMSE)
9	At least 10 scientific publications, at least 2 educational courses (PDAC, IGC), at least 5 new patents filings
10	Reduced environmental impact due to less drilling required
11	Zero accident on mining sites protecting the community and the environment. Zero environmental pollution
12	At least 5 new Copernicus-derived services focusing on mineral detection, safety, geo-hazards, environmental monitoring and operations management

Table 10 presents a summary of the technologies provided by Goldeneye-project together with their effect to different Key Performance Indicators. The summary shows how the Golden AI platform together with the provided technologies has the potential to reach the KPIs defined by the Grant Agreement.

Table 10. Key performance indicators affected with project technologies.

KPI no	Satellite				Drone			Proxy			GNSS location	
	SWIR imaging	Gravitational data	Elevation data	SAR data for anomalies	Fuse Platform	EM survey	Multispectral	TG Raman in-field analysis	TG Raman integrated drilling-unit	Active Hyperspectral sensing	Indoor navigation	Outdoor navigation
1		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓			✓
2	✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓		
3	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓		✓		
4								✓	✓	✓		
5					✓			✓			✓	✓
6	✓			✓				✓	✓		✓	✓
7								✓	✓		✓	✓
8					✓							✓
9	✓			✓		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
10	✓			✓	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		
11	✓		✓	✓			✓				✓	
12	✓	✓	✓	✓			✓					

6. Technical performance indicators

The technical performance indicators of the technologies provided by the project are presented in Table 11. These indicators show the technical performance required to achieve the set KPIs.

Table 11. Technical performance indicators

Sensor placement	Technology	First performance indicator	Value range	Second performance indicator	Value range	Data throughput indicator	Responsible partners
Satellite	SWIR image	Spatial resolution	30 m	Spectral range	1.600-2.430 μ m	SWIR image 1 scena / second	EOS
	Gravitational data (GRACE)	Spatial resolution	0.5-1° (55-111 km at the equator)	Water equivalent thickness	\pm 50 cm	GRACE 1 scena / second	EOS
	Elevation data (DEM, SEM)	Spatial resolution ²³	\sim 12 m (12.37 m at the equator and 12.33 m near the poles)	Relative vertical accuracy ²³	< 2m (slope \leq 20%) < 4m (slope > 20%)	N/A	OPT, DAR
	SAR data (various)	Spatial resolution	SLC, GRD \sim 15x3 m (Sentinel-1); 3x3 m Strip Mode (TSX); 1x1 m SpotMode (TSX)	Polarisation: Single or Dual	(HH or VV) or (HH+HV or VV+VH)	Sentinel- 1 GRD - 10 sq. km /second	OPT,SIN,DAR
	InSAR	Spatial resolution	According to SAR image resolution	Accuracy of deformation results	3-5 mm	N/A	DAR
	Optical satellite Imagery	Spatial resolution	10/20/60 m (band dependent)	Spectral resolution	443-2190 nm	Sentinel-2 - 25 sq.km/second, Sentinel-3 - 10.000 sq. km/ second	SIN
Drone	EM survey	Spatial resolution	20 cm	Frequency of measurement	3000 Hz	1 km ² in 4 hours	RAD
	Multispectral	Spatial resolution	5-20 cm	Spectral range	474 - 980 nm	1km ² in 1 hour	RAD
	Multispectral	Spatial resolution	3-10cm	Spectral resolution	475- 842 nm	1.5km ² in 1 hour	SITE
	Thermal	Spatial resolution ²⁴	3-10 cm	Spectral resolution	9-14 μ m	1.5km ² in 1 hour	SITE
	VIS	Spatial resolution ²⁴	1-8.5 cm	Spectral resolution	400-700 nm	1.5km ² in 1 hour	SITE
Proximity	TG Raman in field analysis	Spectral resolution ²⁵	6 cm ⁻¹	Ability to differentiate minerals ²⁶	\sim 20	60-120 measurement points/hour	VTT
	TG Raman integrated in drilling unit	Spectral resolution ²⁵	6 cm ⁻¹	Ability to differentiate minerals ²⁶	\sim 20	60-120 measurement points/hour	TG
	Active Hyperspectral sensing	Spectral resolution, spatial resolution	16 nm, 1 cm	Ability to differentiate minerals ²⁶	\sim 20	1000 measurement points/ minute.	VTT
	Indoor Navigation	Spatial resolution	2-3 m	turn-by-turn navigation	N/A	N/A	GNS

²³ WorldDEM AirbusDS

²⁴ Maximun flight altitude depends on local drone legislation and also on the camera chosen to be used

²⁵ Instrument response function

²⁶ Total number of minerals to be differentiated during the Goldeneye-project :

Alunitem, amphibole, calcite, clinochlore, dolomite, elbaite, epidote, europium oxide, forsterite, gibbsite, gypsum, illite, jarosite, kaolinite, muscovite, phengite, chlorite, talc, samarium oxide.

7. Conclusions

This deliverable summarizes information about current EOD production techniques for definition of KPIs by analyzing the current state-of-the-art mapping techniques with regard to performance and quality measures. We have provided the information on technologies relevant for the Goldeneye-project and discussed their characteristics in detail (Section 2). The KPIs of the industry have been identified and the positive effect that the project-technologies have on the KPIs are listed in Table 10. We have also provided a listing of Technical performance indicators in Table 11 of the project-technologies. These metrics determine the way the technologies-of-the-project can be utilized in different applications. We conclude, that the Goldeneye-project has the tools and organization to achieve the identified KPIs of the industry.

Appendices

Appendix A. Space assets employed in the Goldeneye-project

Sentinel-2

With more than 9.5M scenes (more than 13.000 added every day) available covering over 90Bn km² of area and containing almost a quadrillion of pixels, Sentinel-2 is becoming one of the most important EO datasets in the world. The Copernicus Sentinel-2 mission carries a medium-to-high spatial resolution²⁷ (10m, 20m and 60m) multi-spectral instrument that covers a wide spectrum (13 bands: 443—2190 nm) with a large swath (290 km) and a high revisit capacity (5 days) globally.

In the scope of the Goldeneye project, cloudless Sentinel-2 images will complement other sources of EO data (InSAR, Gravimetry, Drone-based) in multi-dimensional arrays (Data Cubes).

Figure 10. A heat map of published Sentinel-2 L1C products published per 2019 as reported by SERCO in 2019 Annual Data Access report.

²⁷ Note: spatial resolution is a measure of the system's ability to distinguish between adjacent targets while pixel spacing is the distance between adjacent pixels in an image, measured in meters.

Technical Data from public sources of ESA Documentation:

SENTINEL-2 is a wide-swath, high-resolution, multi-spectral imaging mission, composed of two supporting Copernicus Land Monitoring studies. The mission is based on a constellation of two identical satellites in the same orbit, 180° apart for optimal coverage and data delivery. Together they cover all Earth's land surfaces, large islands, inland and coastal waters every five days at the equator.

The SENTINEL-2 Multispectral Instrument (MSI) samples 13 spectral bands from the Visible (VNIR) and Near Infra-Red (NIR) to the Short Wave Infra-Red (SWIR): 4 x 10 meter Bands (the three classical RGB bands), 6 x 20 meter Bands (4 narrow Bands in the VNIR vegetation red edge spectral domain and 2 wider SWIR bands), and 3 x 60 meter Bands (mainly focused towards cloud screening and atmospheric correction).

Level-1C data is provided as Top-of-atmosphere reflectance in cartographic geometry, whereas Level-2A offers Bottom of Atmosphere (BOA) reflectance images derived from the associated Level-1C products using the Sen2Cor processor. For Level-1C and Level-2A, the granules, also called tiles, are 100x100km² ortho-images in UTM/WGS84 projection.

The Goldeneye project will use a combination of Sentinel-2 Level-1C and Level-2A imagery acquired from both Sentinel-2 A and B satellites. The use of the bands at different resolutions and wavelengths will depend on the application.

Further information can be found in the Sentinel-2 Mission Guide, User Guide, and Technical Guide:
<https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/user-guides>

Sentinel-1

If the observation conditions are poor, the Sentinel-1's SAR technology, makes it possible to measure at any time (day/night), penetrate clouds, analyze soil cover and surface properties, and identify/measure ground deformations. Developed and launched by ESA, it is composed of a constellation of two satellites, Sentinel-1A and Sentinel-1B. It has a wide area range acquisition capabilities of 250 x 250 km per single product.

Technical Data from public sources of ESA Documentation and on Wikipedia:

The mission is composed of a constellation of two satellites, Sentinel-1A and Sentinel-1B, which share the same orbital plane.

The satellites carry a C-band synthetic-aperture radar instrument, which provides a collection of data in all-weather, day or night conditions. The constellation is on a sun synchronous, near-polar (98.18°) orbit.

The orbit has a 12-day repeat cycle and completes 175 orbits per cycle, which results in the temporal resolution of 1-2 days for the northern latitudes of Europe.

IW and EW SLC products have all bursts in all sub-swaths are re-sampled to a common pixel spacing grid in range and azimuth. Single Look Complex products have spatial resolutions that depend on acquisition mode and incidence angles. The equivalent number of independent looks (ENL) for a given product type is intended to correspond to the number of equally weighted, statistically independent looks which would produce the same speckle statistics as the processing used to generate the product.

In the Goldeneye solution, we use Single Look Complex (SLC) imagery from S1 acquired in IW mode. The resulting resolutions are from 2.7x22 m near equator to 3.5x22 m in northern latitudes and pixel spacing 2.3x14.1 m with 1x1 number of looks in az/rng and ENL 1.

Further information can be found in the Sentinel-1 Product Definition document, S1-RS-MDA-52-7440

Figure 11. 'Heat map' of published by 2019 Sentinel-1 SLC products as reported by SERCO in 2019 Annual Data Access report.

In terms of the ground deformation measurement capabilities, the ground resolution accounts for 3 x 20 m with an accuracy in the measurements in the order of 3-5 mm between the pair of acquisitions. It allows to measure deformations up to 80 cm/year. It is not necessary to plan acquisition campaigns as ESA is taking and downloading images, systematically and free of charge, with long-term time series available since 2015. The compromise between accuracy, ground resolution and capability to detect maximum yearly deformations makes Sentinel-1 suitable for

mining areas. Additionally, the wide area range permits to cover large extensions of the earth surface within one image.

With more than 3500 products published per day covering majority of the land mass for typical uses of change detection and interferometric analysis.

Terra-SAR-X & PAZ

TerraSAR-X1 (also referred to as TSX or TSX-1) is a German SAR satellite mission for scientific and commercial applications (national project). The project is supported by BMBF (German Ministry of Education and Science) and managed by DLR (German Aerospace Center). In 2002, EADS Astrium GmbH was awarded a contract to implement the X-band TerraSAR satellite (TerraSAR-X) on the basis of a public-private partnership agreement. In this arrangement, EADS Astrium funded part of the implementation cost of the TerraSAR-X system. In exchange, EADS Astrium/Infoterra received the exclusive commercial exploitation rights for the TerraSAR-X data. The satellite is owned and operated by DLR, and the scientific data rights remain with DLR.

The business goal in this venture is to establish a commercial EO (Earth Observation) market by Infoterra on a sustainable service concept to its customer base. Infoterra, a subsidiary of EADS Astrium, is comprised of Infoterra Ltd. in Farnborough, UK, and Infoterra GmbH in Friedrichshafen, Germany (a subsidiary of EADS Astrium GmbH). Infoterra has established a global distribution network with a range of service options for its customers. A commercial goal is also to provide monitoring services for European initiative GMES (Global Monitoring for Environment and Security).

TerraSAR-X is of SIR-C/X-SAR (1994) and SRTM (2000) heritage - DLR SAR instruments flown on Shuttle missions. The science objectives are to make multi-mode and high-resolution X-band data available for a wide spectrum of scientific applications in such fields as: hydrology, geology, climatology, oceanography, environmental and disaster monitoring, and cartography (DEM generation) making use of interferometry and stereometry.

Features of TerraSAR-X:

Spatial resolution of up to 1 m,
excellent radiometric accuracy,
geometric accuracy unrivalled by any other commercial spaceborne sensor,
quick site access time of 2.5 days max. (2 days at 95% probability) to any point on Earth,
unique agility (rapid switches between imaging modes and polarisations)

TerraSAR-X acquires radar data in the following three main imaging modes:

SpotLight: up to 1 m resolution, scene size 10 km (width) × 5 km (length);
StripMap: up to 3 m resolution, scene size 30 km (width) × 50 km (length);
ScanSAR: up to 16 m resolution, scene size 100 km (width) × 150 km (length);[2]

In addition, the unique design of TerraSAR-X's SAR antenna allows a variety of polarimetric combinations: single or dual polarization and even full polarimetric data takes, are possible.

Depending on the desired application, one of four different product types (processing levels) can be selected

Single Look Slant Range Complex (SSC)
Multi Look Ground Range Detected (MGD)
Geocoded Ellipsoid Corrected (GEC)
Enhanced Ellipsoid Corrected (EEC)

More information can be obtained at: <https://earth.esa.int/web/eoportal/satellite-missions/t/terrasar-x>

With its phased array synthetic aperture radar (SAR) antenna (X-band wavelength 31 mm, frequency 9.6 GHz), TerraSAR-X acquires high-quality radar images of the entire planet whilst circling Earth in a polar orbit at 514 km altitude. The orbit is selected such that the satellite flies in a sun-synchronous dusk-dawn orbit, which means that it moves along the day-night boundary of the Earth and always presents the same face to the sun, ensuring an optimum energy supply via the solar cells. TerraSAR-X is designed to carry out its task for five years, independent of weather conditions and illumination. The satellite has a design life of at least five years and has been operational for 10 years as of summer 2020. This mission is an ongoing mission.

Cosmo Sky MED

Cosmo-SkyMED (Constellation of small Satellites for Mediterranean basin Observation) is an Italian SAR satellite mission managed by ASI (Agenzia Spaziale Italiana) and MoD (Italian Ministry of Defense). Launched in 2010, it is a Dual-Use (Civilian and Defence) end-to-end Earth Observation System that provides data, on demand, for a wide range of applications such as risk management, scientific and commercial applications, among others. Acquisition campaigns must be planned in advance as well as the fees. Data from 2010 to present day is subject to availability.

Technical Data from public sources of COSMO-SkyMed Web Site:

The mission is composed of a constellation of four medium-size satellites, COSMO-SkyMED-1, COSMO-SkyMED-2, COSMO-SkyMED-3 and COSMO-SkyMED-4, orbiting in a sun-synchronous, near-polar (97.86°) orbit at 7620 km height over the Earth surface.

The satellites carry a X-band synthetic-aperture radar instrument which provides a collection of data in all-weather, Day/Night conditions.

The applications of COSMO-SkyMed are focused on military community and civil community (Dual Use), including natural hazards such as floods, landslides and earthquakes. Other applications cover agriculture, forestry, cartography, environment, geology and exploration, telecommunication, etc.

COSMO-SkyMED operates in different modes:

- Spotlight mode: swath width 10x10 km, geometric resolution up to 1 m
- Stripmap mode: swath width 40x40 km, geometric resolution up to 3 m.
- ScanSAR mode: swath width 200x200 km, geometric resolution up to 100 m.

The orbit has a 16-day repeat cycle and completes 237 orbits per cycle. The four satellites provide X-band SAR information, on demand, with a revisiting time of 1-8 days, an accuracy in the measurements in the order of 1 mm, and maximum deformations from 35 to 280 cm/year.

More information can be obtained at: <http://www.cosmo-skymed.it/en/index.htm>

The high accuracy and the capability to detect maximum yearly deformations, relatively small (up to 35 cm/year considering the worst scenario), makes this satellite suitable for urban areas. Several images might be needed due to the small area range (30 x 30 km).

ALOS-2

The Advanced Land Observing Satellite-2 (ALOS-2, also referred to as DAICHI-2) is a Japanese SAR satellite, operated by the JAXA (Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency). It was launched in 2014 with the goal to continue the ALOS “Daichi” program (2006) used for cartography, regional observation, disaster monitoring, and environment monitoring. Acquisition campaigns must be planned in advance as well as the fee for each image. Data from 2014 to present day is subject to availability of images as it mostly covers Asia.

Features of ALOS-2:

The mission is composed of one satellite orbiting in a sun-synchronous sub-recurrent, near polar (97.9°) orbit at 628 km height above the equator. It has a revisiting time of 14 days and a lifetime of 5 years.

The L-band SAR Antenna (PALSAR-2) acquires radar data in the following three main imaging modes:

SpotLight: spatial resolution 1x3 m, scene size 25 km (width) × 25 km (length);

StripMap: up to 3 m resolution, scene size 50 km (width) × 50 km (length);

ScanSAR: up to 60 m resolution, scene size 490 km (width) × 490 km (length);[2]

It has an accuracy in the measurements in the order of 10 mm and a capability to detect deformations up to 140 cm/year.

More information can be obtained at: <https://www.eorc.jaxa.jp/ALOS-2/en/about/overview.htm>

GRACE

GRACE-FO (Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment - Follow-on) provides monthly global Earth gravity field data for processing levels 1B, 2, 3, and 4 with spatial resolution 1°x1° in ASCII Text, NetCDF, and GeoTIFF formats.

Figure 12. Global surface mass anomalies observed by the GRACE-FO satellites and published by Jet Propulsion Laboratory website.

GRACE data surface mass anomalies change in combination with InSAR GRACE data allows to evaluate ground water storage change and earth's surface subsidence as a result of mining activity. GRACE images will complement Sentinel-1 data.

Features of GRACE-FO

(Technical Data from public sources of NASA Documentation and on Wikipedia):

The Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment Follow-On (GRACE-FO) is a continuation of Gravity Recovery and Climate Experiment (GRACE) mission (2002 – 2017) - a joint mission of NASA and the German Aerospace Center (DLR).

The mission is composed of twin satellites follow each other in orbit around the Earth, separated by about 137 miles (220 +/- 50 km), launched in May 2018 and has a design life of 5 years.

GRACE detects changes in the gravity field due to geophysical processes.

Data products

Monthly geopotential models of Earth distributed as spherical harmonic coefficients with a maximum degree of 60 (degree 90 products are also available), monthly land mass grids, monthly global water storage/height anomalies, etc.

Typical latency of the products is 1–2 months.

Processing levels

Level 1B: all necessary inputs to derive monthly time variations in the Earth gravity field; GRACE orbit and mean gravity field determination. Data format: ASCII.

Level 2: estimates of the total month-by-month geopotential of the Earth provided in spherical harmonic coefficients, averaged over approximately a month. Along/Across Track Resolution: 500 km x 500 km. Data format: ASCII.

Level 3. Data products:

- monthly land mass grids contain water mass anomalies given as equivalent water thickness

(TELLUS_GRFO_L3_CSR_RL06_LND_v03, TELLUS_GRFO_L3_GFZ_RL06_LND_v03, TELLUS_GRFO_L3_JPL_RL06_LND_v03).

Longitude/Latitude Resolution: 1 degrees x 1 degrees. Data grids are provided in ASCII/netCDF/GeoTIFF formats;

- monthly ocean bottom pressure anomaly grids (TELLUS_GRFO_L3_CSR_RL06_OCN_v03,

TELLUS_GRFO_L3_JPL_RL06_OCN_v03, TELLUS_GRFO_L3_GFZ_RL06_OCN_v03). Longitude/Latitude Resolution: 1 degrees x 1 degrees. Data grids are provided in ASCII/netCDF/GeoTIFF formats;

- non-tidal high-frequency atmospheric and oceanic mass variation models (GRC-GFO_GRIDDED_AOD1B_JPL_1-DEG_RL06, GRC-GFO_GRIDDED_AOD1B_JPL_MASCON_RL06). Longitude/Latitude Resolution: 1 degrees x 1 degrees;

- gridded monthly global water storage/height anomalies relative to a time-mean (TELLUS_GRAC-GRFO_MASCON_GRID_RL06_V2, TELLUS_GRAC-GRFO_MASCON_CRI_GRID_RL06_V2). Longitude/Latitude Resolution: 0.5 degrees x 0.5 degrees.

Level 4: time series of mass variability averaged over all of the global ocean, Greenland or Antarctica. Longitude/Latitude Resolution: 360 degrees x 180 degrees, 55 degrees x 25 degrees,

360 degrees x 20 degrees.

In the Goldeneye solution we use level 2 data and level 3 spherical harmonic coefficients and monthly land mass grids containing water mass anomalies products.

More information can be obtained at: <https://podaac-tools.jpl.nasa.gov/drive/files/allData/gracefo>

VIIRS

The Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) is a scanning radiometer with 22 spectral bands ranging from 0.41 μm to 12.01 μm , including thermal infrared bands with 750 m spatial resolution.

In the scope of the Goldeneye project, daily VIIRS land surface temperature maps will be used to estimate day/night temperature conditions over mining areas. VIIRS images will complement other EO thermal data sources such as Landsat-8 and ASTER.

Features of VIIRS

(Technical Data from public sources of NASA Documentation and on Wikipedia):

The Suomi National Polar-orbiting Partnership or Suomi NPP, is a weather satellite operated by the United States National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration. It was launched in 2011 and continues to operate on a sun-synchronous orbit 824 km above the Earth. Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite (VIIRS) is one of the five Suomi NPP imaging systems collecting infrared and visible light data.

Swath width: 3060 km.

Bands:

- 16 moderate resolution bands (M-bands) with a spatial resolution of 750m;
- 5 imaging resolution bands (I-bands) with a spatial resolution of 375 m;
- 1 day/night panchromatic band with a spatial resolution of 750m.

In the Goldeneye solution we use VIIRS Land Surface Temperature and Emissivity (LST&E) data products (VNP21) in Collection 1 (C1) retrieved for the three VIIRS thermal infrared bands M14 (8.55 μm), M15 (10.76 μm), and M16 (12 μm).

Land Surface Temperature/Emissivity products:

- VNP21_L2. Layers for LST, quality control, emissivity for bands M14, M15, and M16, LST&E errors, view angle, ASTER Global Emissivity Dataset (GED), Precipitable Water Vapor (PWV), ocean-land mask, latitude, and longitude. Spatial resolution: 750 m. Temporal resolution: < daily. Geographic dimensions: 3060 km x 3060 km. File format: NetCDF4;
- VNP21A1D (Day), VNP21A1N (Night). Contain seven Science Datasets (SDS): LST, quality control, emissivity for bands M14, M15, and M16, view zenith angle, and time of observation. Spatial resolution: 1000 m. Temporal resolution: daily. Geographic dimensions: 1200 km x 1200 km. File format: HDF-EOS5;
- VNP21A2. Contains 11 Science Datasets (SDS): LST, quality control, view zenith angle, and time of observation for both day and night observations along with emissivity for bands M14, M15, and M16. Spatial resolution: 1000 m. Temporal resolution: 8-day. Geographic dimensions: 1200 km x 1200 km. File format: HDF-EOS5.

More information can be obtained at: <https://viirsland.gsfc.nasa.gov/Products/NASA/LSTESDR.html>

Figure 13. Global land surface temperature observed by the VIIRS and published by National Aeronautics and Space Administration, Goddard Space Flight Center website.

ASTER

The Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer (ASTER) is an imaging instrument onboard Terra satellite. ASTER provides images in 14 visible to thermal infrared spectral bands (0.52 – 11.65 μm) at 15, 30, 90 m spatial resolution available from 2000 to present over the globe.

The Level-2 Surface Kinetic Temperature (AST_08) product is generated over the land from the five Thermal Infrared (TIR) bands at 90-m resolution. Under the Goldeneye project ASTER images will complement other EO thermal data sources such as Landsat-8 and VIIRS.

Features of ASTER

(Technical Data from public sources of NASA Documentation and on Wikipedia):

ASTER is one of five remote sensory devices on board the Terra satellite. The instrument has been collecting data since February 2000. The sun synchronous 705 km altitude orbit has a 16-day repeat cycle.

The ASTER instrument consists of three separate instrument subsystems:

- VNIR (Visible Near Infrared bands 1-3), a backward looking telescope which is only used to acquire a stereo pair image;
- SWIR (Short Wave Infrared, bands 4-9), a single fixed aspheric refracting telescope. All SWIR data collected after 1 April 2008 has been marked as unusable;
- TIR (Thermal Infrared, bands 10-14).

Processing levels

Level-1A raw data are reconstructed from Level-0, and are unprocessed instrument digital counts (HDF-EOS format).

Level-1B data are L1A data with the radiometric and geometric coefficients applied.

Level-2 – 10 Standard Data Products: Decorrelation stretch VNIR, SWIR, TIR (AST_06V, AST_06S, AST_06T, spatial resolution – 15, 30, 90 m), Brightness temperature (AST_04, spatial resolution – 90 m), Surface reflectance VNIR, SWIR (AST_07, spatial resolution – 15, 30 m), Surface radiance VNIR, SWIR, TIR (AST_09, AST_09T, spatial resolution – 15, 30, 90 m), Surface emissivity (AST_05, spatial resolution – 90 m), Surface kinetic temperature (AST_08, spatial resolution – 90 m), Polar surface and cloud classification (AST13POL, spatial resolution – 15, 30, 90 m).

Level-3 - Digital elevation model (AST14DEM, spatial resolution – 30 m).

In the Goldeneye solution we use ASTER Surface Kinetic Temperature (AST_08) product provided by NASA Earthdata Search service (search.earthdata.nasa.gov) by request in HDF-EOS or GeoTIFF formats. Depending on location, non-periodical data are available, several granules per year (for example, for Oulu (Finland), 50 granules are available from 20.04.2001 to 15.07.2020).

More information can be obtained at:

https://asterweb.jpl.nasa.gov/content/03_data/04_Documents/aster_user_guide_v2.pdf

Thematic EoD processing platforms

The growing number of remote sensing bands also adds significant complexity. The vast amount of data makes it difficult to work with traditional human analyst based methods.

The access to the data collected by Sentinels and Copernicus Contributing Mission Entities (CCME) is coordinated by ESA in the framework of the Copernicus Data Warehouse. Another element which provides the necessary tools and functions to the data users who need access to the CCME is the Copernicus Contributing Missions Access Support Functions and Platforms.

Appendix B. Digital elevation models

DEM

EU-DEM²⁸

The EU Digital Elevation Model (EU-DEM) is a digital surface model (DSM) representing the first surface as illuminated by the sensors, distributed by Copernicus Land Monitoring Service and managed by the European Commission/DG Enterprise and Industry. The extent of the DSM covers 33 EEA members and 6 cooperating countries²⁹. The EU-DEM combines data from SRTM, ASTER, and freely available Russian topographic maps by fusing the data based on a weighted averaging approach. The data is distributed in 100x100 km tiles, each 4000x4000 pixels at a resolution of 25m. The statistical validation of the product show that the product has an overall vertical accuracy of 2.9m (RMSE) for version 1.0. An improved version 1.1 was released in April 2016, which enhances the correction of geo-positioning issues, removes artifacts, and thus improves the vertical accuracy of EU-DEM using ICESat as reference. However, version 1.1 has not yet been validated.

Table 12. EU-DEM product descriptions.

DEM Product	Product Description
EU-DEM v 1.0	The EU-DEM v1.0 is derived from an automated data fusion process using SRTM and ASTER GDEM digital surface model (DSM) data. Intermap's NEXTMap Europe dataset is utilized to remove any consistent horizontal bias in the GDEM data. The EU-DEM v1.0 is edited to ensure that water features are adequately represented and consistent with the hydrography layer. Residual clouds within the GDEM data are identified and removed same as suspect data extremely differing from the SRTM data. All EU-DEM tiles are edited interactively in a 3D stereo environment. The editing is restricted to the hydrographical features and pits and bumps. In areas above 60 degrees North, the EU-DEM generation process is supported by other DEM data sources provided by the JRC. Water features are flattened (oceans, lakes) and stepped (rivers) based on the hydrography data.
EU-DEM v 1.1	The EU-DEM v1.1 is a resulting dataset of the EU-DEM v1.0 upgrade which enhances the correction of geo-

²⁸ <https://land.copernicus.eu/imagery-in-situ/eu-dem>

²⁹ https://land.copernicus.eu/user-corner/publications/eu-dem-flyer/at_download/file

	positioning issues, reducing the number of artefacts, improving the vertical accuracy of EU-DEM using ICESat as reference and ensuring consistency with EU-Hydro public beta.	
Specification Parameter	Value	
File Format	GeoTIFF	
Data Type	32 Bit, floating	
NoData Value	-32767.0	
Projection	Geographic Coordinates	
Coordinate Reference System	Horizontal	ETRS89
	Vertical	EVRS2000
Pixel Spacing	25 m	
Vertical Unit	Meter	

WorldDEM™ from Airbus DS³⁰

WorldDEM™ is a Digital Elevation Model offered by Airbus Defense and Space that covers 150 Million square kilometres of land area, which is the entire land surface of the Earth. It is one of the most homogenous and accurate elevation models.

The WorldDEM™ products are based on the radar satellite data acquired during the TanDEM-X Mission, which was funded by a Public Private Partnership between the German State, represented by the German Aerospace Centre (DLR) and Airbus Defense and Space. The operation of the satellites in orbit, the data acquisition as well as the interferometric processing of the data was performed by DLR. Airbus Defense and Space refined the processed data and offers the WorldDEM™ data commercially.

The primary goal of the mission was a worldwide (97% of global landmass), consistent, and high precision Digital Surface Model (DSM) based on SAR interferometry. The two satellites TerraSAR-X and TanDEM-X operate as a single-pass SAR interferometer (InSAR), using the bi-static InSAR StripMap mode. The data acquisition started in December 2010 and was complete by mid-2014. The continuous, block-wise data processing at DLR started in December 2013 and lasted until mid-2016.

Table 13. WorldDEM product descriptions.

DEM Product	Product Description
WorldDEM _{CORE}	This Digital Surface Model (DSM) represents the unedited DSM output of the interferometric processing without any refinement (editing). It provides the DEM of the surface of the Earth including buildings, infrastructure and vegetation. This product usually contains radar specific artefacts, voids and may include processing artefacts.

³⁰ WorldDEM™ public specifications document.

WorldDEM™	This product is a refined DSM ensuring hydrological consistency, i.e. flattening of water bodies and consistent flow of rivers, and includes editing of shore- and coastlines.	
WorldDEM DTM	Digital Terrain Model (DTM) representing bare Earth terrain without obstruction features above ground.	
Specification Parameter		
Value		
File Format	GeoTIFF .	
Data Type	32 Bit, floating	
NoData Value	-32767.0	
Projection	Geographic Coordinates	
Coordinate Reference System	Horizontal	WGS84-G1150
	Vertical	EGM2008
Pixel Spacing	0.4 arcsec (approx. 12m)	
Vertical Unit	Meter	

Appendix C: European data cube facility

The European Data Cube Facility, also known as ESA Data Cube Facility, is a project funded by ESA for the service which is providing fast access to a considerable amount of EO information from instrument data up to environmental variables and in order to establish a “bridge from Space to Applications”.

Figure 14. ESA and Copernicus EO Platforms ecosystem (image copyrights of ESA).

Euro Data Cube (<https://eurodatacube.com/>) is an Open EO platform that bridges the link between satellite data and added-value applications. The principal role of the platform is to convert large volumes of geospatial data present on cloud-based infrastructures such as DIAS-es to analysis-ready data that can be used for decision-making, as well as providing the facilities to analyse the data and

disseminate the results. Indeed, the Euro Data Cube is a combination of different EO services, that allows users to 1) access global archives of analysis-ready data, including Copernicus EoD through Sentinel Hub's on-demand access service, 2) analyse the data in the cloud or within the online workspace, based on Sentinel Hub's solutions (API and Batch Processing for heavy-duty tasks) and xcube (<https://github.com/dcs4cop/xcube/>), an xarray-based EO data cube toolkit, 3) distribute results and collaborate, by sharing algorithms or datasets via the Marketplace. Euro Data Cube is designed to maximise interoperability within ESA's network of resources (see below).

ESA NETWORK OF RESOURCES

ESA Network of Resources (NOR) is a combination of exploitation platforms hosting EO data and ICT resources enabling the platform users to procure various data and analytical services from entire ESA and Copernicus EO platforms ecosystem. From a European perspective an EO ecosystem can be identified by four layers as shown in Figure 14 above. The Resource Tier layer – the subject of NOR - consists of the various data sets, the 'Infrastructure as a Service' (IaaS), and low level 'Platform as a Service' (PaaS), which are closely linked to the underlying ICT services e.g. servers, network, operating systems and databases.

ESA intends to procure Resource Tier and Platform services for EO exploitation activities from various existing European Earth Observation Resource Providers for Copernicus and Contributing missions data and to incentivize this 'Network of Resources' and to contribute to a common framework harmonizing service offerings to the end users. The compilation of the portfolio of the available services will be delivered via the various Resource Providers who are pre-qualified through the open tendering procedure of ESA.

The Goldeneye project will explore the possibilities for use and re-use of the ESA NOR via Euro Data Cube integration track, in which SIN partner is a prime contractor for delivery of the service to the ESA .

Due to high requirements for the direct integration with Copernicus Data platforms, the Goldeneye will mostly rely on Copernicus Data Information Access Systems (DIAS), especially in the early stages of the project. DIAS-es are storing the data and making it available in the cloud, but to apply it to a target area, one still has to process the data, requiring broad and diverse remote sensing, physics and geology, big data analytics and (cloud) high performance computing expertise.

Five DIAS cloud-based platforms were officially launched by the European Commission to facilitate and standardize access to Copernicus EO data.

1. MUNDI

Mundi (<https://mundiwebservices.com/>) provides access to data (searching, viewing and download services) from Sentinel-1, 2, 3 and 5P, as well as Landsat-7 and 8, and the six thematic streams of Copernicus services (EMS, CAMS, CLMS, CMEMS, C3S and security) via an online catalog. The catalog covers the full temporal archive for all products, but only offers data over Europe for Sentinel-2 and

Landsat-8 and has a limited retention period outside of Europe for the other data sources. The platform also offers a set of cloud infrastructures based on the Open Telekom Cloud, encompassing on-demand storage and cloud-processing options via virtual machines.

2. CREODIAS

CREODIAS is operated by CloudFerro - a Polish technological company offering services for European and foreign customers. They provide computing power and storage space in a infrastructure as a service model (IaaS).

CREODIAS platform provides public and private cloud for businesses, public institutions and other IT operators based on Open Source solutions and delivers the environment for Big Data processing & visualization – especially for Earth Observation data with idea of putting close together big data & big processing power easily accessible by the customers.

Services provided by CREODIAS platform:

Public and private computing cloud based on OpenStack with all the key elements such as virtual machines (VM), dedicated servers Virtual Machines (dsVM) and many others; Dedicated servers for lease: our bare-metal servers which can be linked to cloud services; Storage services on magnetic disks and SSD, in volume and object storage mode; Wide range of additional services, among others: virtual devices (Load Balancer, FireWall, etc.), leasing of IP addresses, anti DDoS security, direct transmission connections to client's locations, and many others.

CREODIAS will provide the Goldeneye project with: Full IaaS in one place: computing cloud, private cloud, dedicated servers, hybrid solutions - fully configurable, according to the project's needs.

3. ONDA

ONDA (<https://www.onda-dias.eu/>) offers data search, viewing, and download functionalities for the full archive of the current Sentinel fleet (1, 2, 3 and 5P, excluding NRT products), as well as for Envisat (data from January 2007 to January 2010), Landsat 8 (since April 2018) and commercial satellites (KOMPSAT, Deimos-2, and the Maxar constellation). In addition, the data from the CLMS (since June 2019) and CAMS (since April 2019) Copernicus services are available via the platform. Sentinel images older than two months are stored on the ONDA cloud archive, which leads to latency in the retrievals. ONDA also offers cloud-based services, with access to Virtual Servers on which can be deployed processing tools, development tools or a remote desktop. Furthermore, the DIAS offers Data Hosting solutions, where users can store and share their data.

The Goldeneye project will integrate and upgrade the real-time processing of the Sentinel Hub service from SIN (already running on four out of five DIAS platforms, and supplying near real time data to Digital Earth Australia) with on-demand data fusion and analysis ready data cube generation capabilities from OPT. The services will make it more efficient to exploit Copernicus and ESA contributing missions rich multi-sensor data to observe changes in the land, the former providing tremendous breadth and scale of available data and the latter one deep AI enabled analysis tools. Real-time and on-demand data cube technology, powered by parallel processing, will support analysis on massive scale of the data in short period of time. The project will demonstrate how a mining industry end-user can work on the non-qualified problem by creating its own morphological or statistical analysis in a matter of seconds, performing comparison of data from different multi-dimensional sensors through various time segments, and exporting the results into an online data visualization platform (Golden AI project demonstrator) or any other OGC standards compliant GIS tool or as a raster file for post-processing.

The solution will make available a full (multi-temporal and multi-spectral) Sentinel archive¹⁰, accessible via a backend analytical engine and will present the results and the Golden Eye demonstrator web GUI service, which will make it possible to query and identify the necessary Sentinel data anywhere in the world and fuse it among various missions as well as with other data streams, such as Very High Resolution (e.g. Airbus Terra-SAR) satellite data and aerial drone data as required by the user's needs as defined in the use cases.